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Balancing variable renewable electricity generation using combined heat and power plants, large-scale heat pumps, and thermal energy storages in Swedish district heating systems

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Abstract

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The global ambitions to hamper the greenhouse effect has led to ambitious targets for increasing renewable energy use. This, in combination with recent years' vast development of wind and solar power, implies that there will be significant amounts of variable renewable electricity (VRE) in future energy systems. With the inherent variability in VRE production comes a need for increased contingency in power systems. This requires both controllable production and consumption of power to cope with VRE deficits and surpluses. The purpose of this doctoral thesis is to investigate the potential for providing such power balancing services from Swedish district heating systems (DHS). Analyses are made for different system levels: community, regional, and national. Computer simulations of DH production systems with combined heat and power (CHP) plants, heat pumps, and thermal energy storage (TES), operated to supply a power balancing demand, are here shown to potentially reduce VRE deficits and surpluses. The results further show that reducing peak deficits and/or surpluses mainly depends on the installed capacities in CHP units and/or heat pumps. However, annual deficits or surpluses are reduced more if the system includes a TES. Also, the shares of wind and solar power in VRE mixes are shown to be relevant for fuel use and system performance. Solar-dominated VRE promotes heat pumps, reduces fuel use in CHP, and motivates a seasonal operation of TESs. Wind-dominated VRE matches with high capacities in CHP units, yields increased fuel use and motivates short-term operation of TESs. A crucial limitation is competition for the heat load between heat pumps and CHP units, which reduces the potential for CHP production. Competition between stored heat and heat pumps also occurs in systems with smaller TESs and large amounts of surplus electricity. In order for power balancing services to be economically viable for DHS operators, changed market structures that appropriately value the delivered services are likely required. The overall conclusions are: DHSs can offer power balancing, a high share of PV is essential to reduce fuel use, and finally, seasonal TESs are needed to cope with large amounts of surplus heat and/or replacement of peak load units.

Keywords: District heating systems, Power-to-Heat, Heat pumps, Combined heat and power, Thermal energy storage, Power balance, Variable renewable electricity, Biomass fuel

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*“You may never know what results come of your actions,
but if you do nothing, there will be no results.”*
-Mahatma Gandhi

List of Papers

This thesis is based on the following Papers, which are referred to in the text by their Roman numerals.

- I. **Monie, S.**, Nilsson, M. A., Widén, J., Åberg, M. (2020). A residential community-level virtual power plant to balance variable renewable power generation in Sweden. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 228:113597
- II. **Monie, S.**, Nilsson, M. A., Åberg, M. (2020). Comparing electricity balancing capacity, emissions, and cost for three different storage-based local energy systems. *IET Renewable Power Generation*, Vol. 14(19):3936-3945
- III. **Monie, S.**, Åberg, M. (2021) Power balancing capacity and biomass demand from flexible district heating production to balance variable renewable power generation. *Smart Energy*, 4:100051
- IV. **Monie, S.**, Åberg, M. (2021) Potential for existing rock caverns in Sweden to be used as flexible district heating loads to alleviate the inherent net load variability from renewable energy. *Manuscript*.
- V. **Monie, S.**, Hesamzadeh, R., M., Åberg, M. (2021) Power-to-Heat on the reserve capacity market – policy implications considering economic constraints and competing heat production. Submitted to *Energy Policy*.

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Publications not included in the thesis

- VI. **Monie, S.**, Nilsson, M. A., Lingfors, D., Widén, J., Åberg, M. (2018). Thermal Energy Storages in Residential Areas – a potential to increase renewable power generation? In proceedings of the *ACEEE Summer Study on Energy Efficiency in Buildings*, Pacific Grove, CA, USA, 12 – 17 August 2018.
- VII. **Monie, S.**, Nilsson, M. A., Åberg, M. (2019). Electricity balancing capacity, emissions, and cost comparison of three storage-based local energy systems for variable power generation. In proceedings of the *9th International Workshop on Integration of Solar Power and Storage into Power Systems*, Dublin, Ireland, 15 – 16 October 2019.

Notes on my contributions

I contributed the following to the appended Papers:

Paper I., I developed the model, did the simulations and wrote sections 2 – 5.

Paper II., I developed the comparative algorithm used, did the simulations and wrote most of the Paper.

Paper III., I developed the model and did the simulations of the power balancing production, I wrote major part of the Paper.

Paper IV., I did the heat transfer simulations, I did the data collection and compilation, I wrote the Paper.

Paper V., I did the data collection and compilation, I developed the algorithm and did the simulations, I wrote the Paper.

Ethical considerations of research

As a researcher you are on a quest for knowledge. Regardless of field you formulate a hypothesis and then you try to falsify it. Depending on the outcome you might reformulate the hypothesis and the process continuous iteratively. Somewhere along the way a result emerges that can contribute to the community of science and knowledge. The result is presented and set out on the ocean of society's applications. There it ends, from the researcher's point of view. New knowledge has been put forth and what society uses this for lies in the hands of society. As long as you, as a researcher, have been truthful and clearly stated your methods, you are ethically immaculate.

But where does a researcher's responsibility really end? In the *Uppsala Code of Ethics for Scientists* researchers pledge to a codex stating that they will not participate in any research that may contribute to harmful applications, e.g., warfare or environmentally hazardous. This is noble, and in a way deeply responsible, but perhaps it is also, in a way, making it a bit too easy for oneself – from an ethical point of view. By simply stating that 'I will not take part in this', one is on one hand not to blame if things turn out to the worst, but on the other hand without any possibility to control the damage done, and perhaps, most importantly, should we let research subjects that may have dual effects (both potentially good and bad) be left to those with no scruples? To be ethically responsible is not always just to say no and turn your back on the problem, sometimes it requires that you get your hands dirty and really work with it to prevent the worst from happening. This is of course a jeopardy if you are alone in the project with your point of view. Then again, this is not an appeal for us to deliberately engage in research projects just because they might have a questionable outcome. It is an encouragement to all fellow researchers to scrutinize their own work and responsibly try to take precautions to avoid ethical predicaments.

It is easy to look back and determine what went well and what didn't, but I'd say it could be more important to look forward instead. To be ethically responsible one should try to identify ethical impacts from one's research. With an ethical impact assessment based on forecasting one can try to identify both the anticipated benefits and their ethical impacts, but also what can be less desirable, maybe even unwanted. Here it is of relevance to look at historical projects on similar tasks through literature studies and then document the findings. Next, one must evaluate the results, via expert consultation, desk

research or participatory methods. Determine the likelihood for different effects, try to grade the relative importance (i.e. might it happen once in a century, but lead to draught? Or may it occur every year, but only cause disturbing noise?). Identify potential or actual value conflicts – try to see if these could be resolved. Conceptualize the relevant ethical impacts that needs to be addressed. Look for remedial actions that might be found within related research to reduce or avoid negative ethical impacts. Formulate design improvements and relevant recommendations for the project. Now go back and review the research project and audit the relevant sections.

By performing such a self-assessment¹ the researcher becomes aware of ethical issues in the project. It is only by becoming aware that we can make a difference.

¹ As suggested by the SATORI-project (<http://satoriproject.eu/framework/section-5-ethical-impact-assessment/>)

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Abbreviations

BAPV	Building applied photovoltaics
CHP	Combine heat and power
DH(S)	District heating (system)
DSM	Demand side management
EES	Electric energy storage
GHG	Greenhouse gas
HoB	Heat-only boiler
HP	Heat pumps
IRR	Internal rate of return
IWH	Industrial waste heat recovery
MSW	Municipal solid waste
NPV	Net present value
NRL	Negative residual load
P2H	Power to heat
PI	Profitability index
PRL	Positive residual load
PV	Photovoltaics
PVR	Present value ratio
SA:V	Surface-area-to-volume ratio
TES	Thermal energy storage
V:SA	Volume-to-surface-area ratio
VPP	Virtual power plant
VRE	Variable renewable electricity
WtE	Waste incineration (Waste-to-Energy)

1. Introduction

Since pre-industrial times, the use of fossil energy has contributed to a global greenhouse effect with drastically increased levels of CO₂ in the atmosphere [1]. The majority of the members of the international community have, through ratification of the Paris Agreement, promised to reduce greenhouse gas emissions [2]. One way to achieve reduced emissions is by increasing the share of electricity production from renewable energy sources such as wind, solar, hydro, and biomass. However, in Sweden the hydro power capacity cannot be further increased and biomass is a limited resource. Electricity production from wind and solar is, however, weather dependent, which means that it is not the electricity demand that primarily determines when the electricity is produced. With a large-scale phasing out of non-renewable power (such as oil, coal, natural gas, and nuclear power), compensated by increased variable renewable electricity (VRE) production, a need for reserve power capacity to cover VRE power supply deficits will follow [3]. During favourable weather conditions, there is, on the other hand, risk for VRE production to exceed the power demand. Locally, this can lead to impairment of the power quality if the VRE production is not disconnected. To handle these VRE production and demand mismatches, various measures can be taken, such as strengthening transmission capacities, implementing storages, or creating flexible loads that can match electricity surpluses.

Another challenge for future power supply is related to urbanization and transmission capacities. Cities with a growing population require increased access to electric power. As the electrification of transports and new establishments of electricity-intensive industries are taking place, the load on the transmission lines into the cities is increased [4]. However, the physical power cables into the cities have limited transmission capacity. This means that increased power production capacity outside cities will not necessarily be able to supply increased power demands within the cities. Therefore, limited power generation capacity within urban areas is likely a future concern. A growing interest in installing photovoltaics (PV) in urban areas surely increases power production on “the inside” of the transmission capacity limitations. Some cities even require that new properties must be provided with PV (Paris, New York) [5]. However, the absence of temporal matching between PV production and demand, as mentioned above, means that PV power generation is no

guarantee for alleviated capacity shortage. Additional power supply for covering production shortages is needed.

In urban built environments with high heating demands, there may be economically viable conditions for district heating systems (DHS). District heating is often produced in thermal plants by combustion of solid, liquid, or gaseous fuels [6]. In this work, the focus is on DHSs with biomass-based production. In DHSs, it is common with combined heat and power (CHP) plants that co-produce heat and electricity, a way to reach a high overall fuel conversion efficiency. The production is potentially environmentally friendly depending on the type of fuel, the degree of flue gas cleaning, and the handling of the residual products. CHP is a controllable power production capacity that is typically placed within urban areas and therefore potentially contributes to reducing problems with the transmission capacity shortages.

In a conventional heating plant, fuel is used to produce heat. However, compressor heat pumps and electric boilers are well-established large-scale alternative heat production technologies. Since electricity is consumed in these, there is a possibility to use heat pumps and electric boilers, often referred to as power-to-heat (P2H), as a flexible electric load (e.g., acting on the automatic primary reserve market) [7]. DHSs with heat pumps or electric boilers and CHP units can potentially be operated to cover VRE production deficits and to consume VRE production surpluses. However, a sufficient heat load is necessary for heat production from both CHP and heat pumps to be efficient. Heat loads in DHSs consist mainly of heat demand for space heating in buildings, and therefore, the load varies significantly between seasons. Thus, the heat load level limits the CHP and heat pump production. The inclusion of large-scale thermal energy storage (TES) can, however, increase the flexibility of the heat load [8]. This flexibility can also enable the DHS utility operator to easier reach production targets based on biddings set on the day-ahead market and/or as part of the reserve capacity market [9], [10]. The work presented in this thesis investigates if a DHS with CHP, heat pumps, and TES could be operated to contribute with increased power balancing flexibility in a future energy system with a large share of VRE.

Typically, DHSs are operated to supply the heating demand [11], and if they include a CHP plant, these can co-produce electricity when electricity prices are high enough to cover the increased cost of fuel consumption. Electricity production is thus to some extent a by-product of the main business model, i.e., heat production. With the stated intention of setting electricity balancing services as the primary target of production, the system operation is no longer what can be considered typical for DHSs [12]. A DHS consisting of a CHP unit, heat pumps and large-scale TES operated in such a way is similar to what is often referred to as Smart Energy Systems. The term smart energy system implies that different energy sectors work in a coordinated way to achieve higher system efficiency [13]. This coordination could for example involve industrial waste heat used to supply heat demand in a DH network, or

it can involve the consumption of surplus electricity in heat pumps to produce heat while the electricity consumption contributes to electricity balancing. This holistic approach where resources from different sectors are coordinated, e.g., surplus power in the electricity system is used to power heat pumps in the DH sector, is used in all power balancing system configurations studied in this thesis.

Further aspects that are relevant to consider, besides dimensioning production units to cover specified demands, are, for example, costs and environmental impact. For example, using biomass as solid fuel for combustion, competes with other potential uses of biomass, such as petrochemical substitute, fuel for transports, and building materials. Since biomass is a limited resource this is an important aspect. Furthermore, storing heat comes with storage losses that inevitably must be covered by increased heat production. This could induce increased demand for biomass compared to a system where heat is produced without using a storage. To avoid such negative impacts, it becomes relevant with other carbon-neutral sources for heat production, e.g., heat pumps that use surplus electricity from wind and solar.

The concept of Smart Energy Systems could be a key for DHSs to reach synergy effects as multi-carrier power balancing systems, i.e., heat production in heat pumps for power balancing services while also reduce the fuel demand for heat production in CHP units, in a future scenario with high shares of VRE. With the possibility to provide both positive and negative power balancing production in CHP units and heat pumps, enabled by TESs as a flexible heat load, such systems may remedy congestion and capacity related power issues in urban areas.

1.1 Aims of the thesis

The main purpose of this thesis is to examine if DHSs consisting of CHP, heat pumps (HP), TES and a DH distribution network can achieve increased flexibility that promotes positive and negative power balancing and thereby contribute to the integration of large shares of VRE generation in the energy system. This is investigated on different system levels and with varying shares of VRE in the electricity production system. The following sub-aims has been formulated to reach the main aim:

- I. Investigate the possibility for DHSs in Sweden to provide power balancing with a production strategy that follows an electricity balancing demand.
- II. Identify factors that limits the power balancing services in such a power balancing system.

- III. Analyse how the fuel use is affected when comparing a power balancing DHS including HPs and large-scale TES with a conventional DHS with a traditional heat production strategy.
- IV. Analyse the economic possibilities for implementing a power balancing system with CHP, HP and TES under current economic conditions.

1.2 Overview of the appended Papers

Here follows a brief description of the main focus of research in respective appended Paper.

Paper I present a residential community-level coupled heat and electricity system that couples thermal and electrical energy systems. The system is operated to follow an electricity balancing demand. The study investigates how this system can offer power balancing production under varying shares of VRE.

Paper II makes a comparison between the system simulated in Paper I and two other storage-based energy system setups. These are evaluated regarding power balancing performance, emissions of greenhouse gases (GHG) and economic feasibility. The two additional systems consist of one "Business-as-usual" case with DH and a battery storage instead of a TES, and one fully electrified system with battery storage and, instead of DH, individual heat pumps at end-user level.

Paper III takes the power balancing services to a higher system level and investigates the potential for flexible power balancing services as well as impact on fuel demand for several aggregated DHSs within a common electricity price area in Sweden, SE3. A "Business-as-usual" case is compared with the same setup, but with TES added and changed operational strategy that follows the electricity balancing demand, and a second scenario where all heat-only-boilers (HoB) are converted to CHP units.

Paper IV is a study of how existing rock caverns formerly used as depots for fossil oil, but converted into TESs, can act as flexible heat loads and enable the heating sector to provide power balancing services. The study investigates the potential for this in all four electricity price regions of Sweden assuming that all rock caverns are in close vicinity to a sufficient heat load. A generic city scale heat demand is simulated with access to one or two rock caverns converted to TES. The study focuses on dimensioning the CHP and heat pumps for maximal reduction of the net load variability. Also, the fuel demand is considered.

Paper V investigates the potential for district heating utilities to place P2H-capacities on the reserve capacity market. Three different DHS configurations are simulated. One that only contains HoB, one system consisting of base load production from industrial waste heat (IWH) and waste incineration together with biomass fuelled CHP and peak demand HoB. The third configuration consist of only biomass fuelled CHP units. All systems apply P2H as a parallel production with access to rock cavern TESs. The economic potential of bidding on the capacity market is investigated by calculating the cost changes of district heating operators when production, heat and electricity, is replaced by heat produced in P2H units.

1.3 Definition of terms

The following terminology occurs frequently in the following work and is therefore defined:

- Throughout this work both heat and electricity will be discussed. To clearly differentiate between these two forms of energy it will always be indexed with $_{el}$ for electricity or $_{th}$ for thermal energy (heat).
- Power balancing demand: The electricity consumption subtracted with the electricity production yields a theoretical intermediate net load profile with either remaining electricity demand or surplus electricity.
- Positive residual load, PRL: The remaining electricity demand that must be supplied with more electricity production. Measured in W (power demand) or Wh (electricity demand).
- Negative residual load, NRL: The surplus electricity production (which becomes a negative value when defined as above) that needs to be consumed by flexible load, stored or curtailed. Measured in W (power surplus) or Wh (electricity surplus).
- Power balancing services: Production or consumption of electricity depending on whether the power balancing demand is positive, there is a PRL, or negative, there is an NRL. Units that may provide this service are for instance CHP plants (production) or heat pumps (consumption).
- Smart Energy System: systems in which the coupling of different energy carrying sectors can achieve synergies. For instance, replacement of solid fuel for heat production by recovered waste heat from industry or power consumption in heat pumps to balance power systems.

- Power balancing system: a system with CHP, P2H, and large-scale TES, for production and/or consumption of electricity as a power balancing service, further enabled by the access to a TES. Such a system is here considered a variant of a smart energy system.

2 Background

In this chapter a brief background is given to put the work presented in this thesis into a relevant context. Section 2.1 describes the transition the energy system is expected to undertake and what challenges this may bring due to variability and increased demand for power balancing services. District heating as system is briefly described in Section 2.2 along with its future possible part in the concept of Smart Energy Systems. In Section 2.3 relevant technologies applicable in a smart energy system used in the work presented in this thesis is presented. Finally, in Section 2.4 relevant research gaps identified is presented.

2.1 Energy systems in transition

As described in the introduction, we are in a time where the anthropogenic impact on the climate causes demands for changes in energy use. Changes that replace fossil energy resources adding GHG to the biosphere with renewable energy resources. In its latest report [14], the IPCC stated that:

It is unequivocal that human influence has warmed the atmosphere, ocean and land. Widespread and rapid changes in the atmosphere, ocean, cryosphere and biosphere have occurred.

An area-graph showing that the share of fossil energy resources have been fairly stable during the last three decades. During the last ten years, the shares for renewables have increased slightly. Globally, the total energy supply has

Figure 2.1. Relative shares of global energy supply between 1990 and 2019 [15].

increased between 1990 and 2019 by 165%. With a share of fossil fuels constantly about 80% of the total, as shown in Figure 2.1. Fossil energy resources all contribute to GHG emissions regardless of where, for what, and by whom they are used. According to the IEA, electricity and heat producers account for just over 40% of GHG emissions, the transport sector accounts for almost 25%, and the industrial sector accounts for just under 20% [15]. In Figure 2.2 it can be seen that the consumption of electricity has more than doubled since 1990, mainly made possible by increased use of fossil fuels, but there has also been a significant increase in renewable energies during the same period. The proportion of renewable energies has tripled and VRE has increased almost exponentially. Relative to total electricity production, VRE accounts for merely 8%. Locally, this however varies significantly. In Denmark, for example, the proportion of electricity produced by wind power has passed 50% of total electricity production. In 2019, Swedish wind power accounted for just over 10% of total electricity production, hydro and nuclear power each produced 40% and the remaining 10% was thermal power [16].

Figure 2.2. Global electricity generation where a) shows electricity generation by source and b) electricity generation from VRE in detail [15].

2.1.1 Variable renewable electricity (VRE)

In an electricity system, production and consumption must always match instantaneously [17]. Traditionally, the electricity system can be described as consisting of controllable production that supply a variable demand. However, in the future, the same variable demand is supposed to be supplied with an increasing share of likewise variable VRE production. Controllable power production can be planned, started, regulated, and stopped on the basis of demand. Wind and solar power are limited in this respect to always being able to stop, sometimes to start, but not to be fully planned. Wind and solar power are both variable, but in different ways.

Solar power has seasonal and daily patterns that are partly linked to geospatial circumstances. At high latitudes, for example, the seasonal variation is large. These patterns facilitate planning for when solar power can be expected to produce, however, there is always a risk that solar panels are shaded by clouds. These shadows cause power output variations, sometimes rapidly and randomly, and within seconds.

Wind power also have seasonal patterns [18], but not as strongly accentuated as solar power does and to some extent complementary to solar power [19]. Nevertheless, wind power, like solar power, is dependent on the weather, i.e. the wind conditions, but rarely has as rapid variations in production as solar power [18]. Production follows the wind speed, which is generally not abrupt but gradually variable. However, there is a wind speed limit (cut-out speed) where the wind turbines are shut down and turned in irons (alongside with the wind) as a protective measure to prevent the towers from breaking. In these cases, the power output is gradually increased up to maximum capacity, after which the output is abruptly stopped [20]. This could lead to instant power shortage and requires a rapid increase in electricity generation from other technologies.

Aggregated production variations for both solar and wind power are evened out with large numbers of generating units and, not least, significant geographical distribution, a so-called "smoothing effect" [18], [21]. This can be utilized to the extent that is allowed by the physical transmission capacities of the power system. Power distribution constraints exist at all levels of the power distribution system and the effects of these constraints are manifested in different ways. For example, there are so-called bottlenecks in the national transmission lines that limit transmission capacity between the northern and southern parts of Sweden, giving rise to Sweden's four electricity price areas [22]. Similar capacity constraints have been reported from several of Sweden's [23] and Europe's major cities [4]. These constraints mainly concern capacity shortages into the urban environment and means that grid owners cannot guarantee full capacity at all times, for electricity users. Furthermore, there are also a limit on the low voltage side for connection of PV installations, often referred to as "hosting capacity" in the literature [24]. If the hosting capacity level is exceeded, there is a risk of overvoltages and/or overcurrents which can damage electronic components that are connected to the grid [3].

In general, there are no politically defined goals for the shares of wind and/or solar power to be installed in Sweden. There was an energy agreement among most political parties represented in the Swedish parliament, stating that Sweden should achieve 100% renewable electricity production by 2040 [25]. Recently, some parties have chosen to withdraw from the agreement. The agreement still exists, but does not provide explicit targets for the desired installed capacities for electricity supply. In 2020, wind and solar power production accounted for 21% and 0.3% of Sweden's electricity demand respectively [26], which for wind power corresponds to almost a doubling over the

last five years. The national transmission operator and the balance responsible authority, Svenska Kraftnät, describes a possible development to 2040 for the Nordic countries, see Table 2.1., where wind power produced electricity corresponds to 37% of the electricity demand [27]. The Swedish Energy Agency have made an analysis of four possible energy systems scenarios for Sweden in 2050. Two scenarios met 100% renewable electricity generation and included 47% and 28% wind power, and 8% and 13% solar power of the electricity demand, respectively [28]. The Swedish Energy Agency also produce biennial scenarios of likely future developments for the Swedish energy system. These scenarios are, of course, uncertain, but nevertheless give an indication of the direction in which governments and industry expect developments to go. The report ER 2021:6 presents seven different scenarios in which the share of wind power relative to electricity demand varies between 36% and 66% and the share of solar power varies between 4% and 6% [29]. It is fairly clear that there is no consensus on the likely shares of each type of power. Given the cost trend for wind and solar power, which for several years have had the lowest cost of all energy types [30], and the national and international commitments to climate targets, there is reason to assume that the share of wind and solar power in the Swedish energy system will increase. Levels of up to 60% and 10% for wind and solar power respectively relative to electricity demand are not inconceivable. This will, however, pose challenges for the electricity system in terms of reliability, power balancing capability, and reserve capacities.

Table 2.1. *Forecast on share of VRE relative the annual electricity demand in the Swedish energy system.*

Forecast	Wind power	Solar power
Nordic Grid Development Plan 2019, SvK [27]	37%	
Four futures – The Energy system after 2020, SEA [28]	47%	8%
	28%	13%
Scenarios on the Swedish energy system 2020, SEA [29]	36 – 66%	4 – 6%

2.1.2 Power balance services

The Nordic electricity system is synchronously interconnected. This means that all generators, turbines and rotating machines connected to the grid rotate at the same speed or frequency, which is the “grid frequency” of 50 Hz [3]. If there is a change in the balance between power generation and power demand in the power system, the grid frequency is changed. It can be illustrated as a large rotating wheel to which a drive belt is attached. If the load to which the drive belt is connected is large, the wheel will slow down or stop. On the other hand, if the load is suddenly lifted off of the drive belt, the rotation of the wheel will rapidly increase, spinning loose. This allegory is applicable to the

power system in general. The tolerable range for the grid frequency to vary is merely within $\pm 1\%$ before risking damaging equipment and infrastructure [31]. Therefore, the frequency of the power system is constantly monitored and in case of deviations, various power balancing measures are activated [32]. These actions depend on the magnitude of the disturbance and whether the deviation is positive or negative, i.e., increased or decreased frequency. If the disturbance is a sudden increase in consumption the grid frequency will drop and the electricity production needs to increase, and vice versa, if the consumption suddenly drops the grid frequency will increase and electricity production must be reduced. The balance between production and consumption is established through trading on different electricity market areas and for northern Europe this trading takes place at NordPool [33]. NordPool's short-term market consists of three temporally differentiated market areas: the day-ahead market (NordPool spot), the intraday market (Elbas) and the reserve capacity market. The reserve capacity market in turn consists of three market areas which are differentiated by the technical requirements for response time to frequency deviations, but also duration and repeatability [32]. When large shares of VRE are introduced in a power system, this leads to an increased need for flexible contingency in the rest of the power system, i.e., the power system must be able to handle an increasing share of deficits and surpluses in the electricity supply [17].

Under favourable conditions, windy and/or sunny weather, these power sources will produce large amounts of power. At such times, a high share of VRE will mean that more electricity could be produced than what is momentarily needed leading to a surplus of electricity. This is typically handled by exporting the surplus power, provided that transmission capacity is available to a network or region without surplus [34]. The latter is a real dilemma in, for example, Denmark where there is occasionally a need to export surplus wind power and where, at the same time, there is surplus of German wind power [35], [36]. Other ways to deal with situations of surplus electricity are controllable loads that are activated when needed, or disconnection of the generating unit, i.e., curtailment [37]. There is a growing interest in the possibility of storing surpluses in different types of electricity storages [38]. In the longer term, expansion of transmission capacities is also possible. However, both electricity storage and grid reinforcement are both costly and the latter also time-consuming to plan and implement [39].

Unfavourable weather conditions, i.e. no sunlight and no wind, can lead to power shortages. These can be dealt with by increasing other power producers' output, such as hydro or thermal power generation. Other ways to cover deficits are importing electricity or activating energy storage and/or interruptible load, i.e., demand side management.

The means for power balancing production that are investigated in this thesis are power generation in CHP plants and large-scale heat pumps for power consumption, both technologies applied in the DH sector. Traditionally,

power balancing is not the main priority for DH operators [40], but DHSs equipped with CHP plants and/or heat pumps are part of the active electricity market and thus also currently a part of power balancing production/consumption [41]. Today heat is generally produced to meet the DHS heat demand. This means that the level of heat demand limits the power production in CHP plants and/or power consumption in heat pumps. Svenska Kraftnät assessed the availability of different types of power at any given hour in an analysis of power balancing capacities within the Swedish power system [42]. The analysis showed that the CHP plants in the DHSs have a power balancing availability at any hour of the year of about 76.5%. This means that of all installed power generating capacity in the DH sector, a maximum of 76.5% is expected to be available at any hour of the year if more power is needed.

2.2 District heating

District heating systems are central for the work presented in this thesis. In the following section a general description of DHSs is given. This is followed by an overview of the development of DHSs to date and the role the sector expected to have in the future energy system according to the scientific literature. This will lead into the final section of this chapter and the concept of Smart Energy Systems, which, *inter alia*, is defined as the interaction between different energy systems to achieve desirable synergies.

In very simple terms, a DHS can be described as consisting of three parts: (1) a central source of heat that can be produced, recovered, and/or is a natural resource, (2) a heat distribution system that transports the heat to (3) the heat users. The Swedish District Heating Act (2008:263) [43] defines a DHS as an activity that distributes hot water or another heat carrier in pipes to which an undefined group within a geographical area may be connected. The production and sale of heat is also included in the definition of a DHS if this is done by the same operator who also carries out the distribution. An important aspect here is the geographical area. This, in turn, relates to the heat losses in the distribution network. The losses correlate negatively with the heat density of the DH area, *i.e.*, a low heat density (few customers over a large area) yields high relative losses and vice versa; high heat density reduce the relative losses [44]. Hence to the geographical distribution of the network becomes a matter of economic trade-off between the economic loss due to distribution losses and sufficient earnings from the area to supply. A DHS is designed based on the local conditions and needs. This means that systems differ from place to place in terms of production units, local heat resources, and heat load [45]. Common to all systems is that the dimensioning quantity for the operation is the local heat demand, which in turn is determined mainly by the local climate. However, the dimensioning can also be influenced by one or a few large customers that for instance need process heat or district cooling [46].

The mix of production units in a DHS is generally cost optimized [47]. Since heat demands vary throughout the year, it is usually justified to have several different production facilities serving different segments of the production [48], [47]. For example, plants that are expensive to invest in but cheap to operate are usually so-called base-load units. These are, for example, waste incineration plants or CHP plants fuelled by difficult-to-burn residues with high moisture content from the forest industry [49]. Base-load plants generally have many operating hours over the year and are generally only shut down for maintenance in summer during low demand periods. Industrial waste heat is, if available, often part of the base-load production [50]. Base-load units are rarely dimensioned to cover peak load demand as this results in relatively low utilization of the unit's capacity [51]. Normally, one or more units exist as intermediate load units. These are generally facilities with a higher operating cost than base-load units. Typical plants may be CHP plants fired with higher quality fuel (lower moisture content) such as wood chips, peat, or pellets [52]. Electric compressor heat pumps can also be part of intermediate load production [53]. These usually have a more variable operation cost compared to solid fuel as it is determined by the electricity price [11]. Finally, peak load units are used to cover demand peaks in the coldest periods of the year. Typically, these are oil-fired hot water boilers, i.e. only heat is produced and no electricity as in a CHP plant. These units normally have few operating hours during the year due to low investment costs and relatively high operation costs [47].

2.2.1 Generations of district heating

DHSs are generally considered to have been developed through three different generations, with most of the systems in Sweden today being of the third generation [49]. *The 1st generation* of DH used pressurised steam as energy carrier and was introduced in the 1880s in the USA [46]. This first generation was the main technology choice for almost all DH systems until the 1930s. It usually had coal-fired heating plants that produces steam distributed in concrete ducts. Special steam traps and compensators were required to maintain the pressure in the distribution system. This system is usually associated with high heat losses and is now considered obsolete. However, it is still in operation in Manhattan, New York (which is why steam comes out of the streets in films made in Manhattan). In addition to the problem of losses, the steam was returned as condensate, which corroded the pipes and led to less return condensate and reduced energy efficiency. Also, steam explosions could occur, leading to serious accidents and even fatalities [9].

With the introduction of *the 2nd generation* DH in the 1930s, pressurised hot water was introduced with a supply temperature often above 100 °C [54]. The distribution networks still consisted of concrete ducts with in-situ insulation, and the auxiliary equipment was typically material-intensive and large,

e.g., shell-and-tube heat exchangers and heavy-duty valves. This technology was dominant until the 1970s. The advantages of this generation were fuel savings and reduced costs compared to the 1st generation. The 2nd generation introduced hot water storage, central distribution pumps, CHP units and the use of oil as a fuel. On the end-user side, distribution water was circulated directly through the radiators. The 2nd generation was usually part of the government's policy to achieve a coordinated expansion of CHP plants [9].

From the 1970s until today all newly established DHSs are 3rd generation [9]. The introduction of prefabricated insulated twin pipes, is however major differences as well as highly efficient plate exchangers, supply temperatures typically below 100 °C and less material-intensive components in general. As the 3rd generation systems were built there has also, in Sweden, been a change in fuel use [49]. Following the oil crisis in the 1970s, there was a shift from oil to coal and peat, but also to electric resistive boilers and compressor heat pumps due to the establishment of nuclear power which led to a surplus of electricity in Sweden [53]. Also, more lately, environmental awareness gradually led to further changes in fuel use from fossil fuels to biomass and waste and to the inclusion of industrial waste heat as a heat source [49].

For future DHS, there are concepts such as 4th generation (4GDH) and 5th generation of DH and cooling (5GDHC). These are visions and concepts of how DHSs could be part of a sustainable future energy system and what technological transformation this might require [9]. As energy efficiency in the built environment leads to reduced heating demand, 4GDH is by [55] proposed to utilize this by using low temperature distribution systems, where water circulates at temperatures below 50-60°C. At distributed substations, this low temperature water is raised to 70°C via heat pumps. By lowering the supply temperature, the distribution losses will be significantly reduced. In addition, the lowered supply temperature opens up the possibility to include more low temperature waste heat from e.g., cooling processes in commercial buildings. This also means that the distribution network must allow bi-directional flows, which requires more advanced monitoring and more complex dynamic pressure performance, than what is used in the 3rd generation systems. Also, seasonal thermal storages are suggested to store local waste heat or heat from renewable sources.

5GDHC is similar to 4GDH in many respects, for instance the deployment of heat pumps in every substation, but proposes even lower supply temperatures of 30°C and also double piping to allow bi-directional flow of both heat and cooling simultaneously [56]. For both generations, the use of surplus electricity from VRE is suggested to be an essential part of the heat production technology via electric boilers or heat pumps. Moreover, they are both considered as *Smart thermal grids* and as such integrated with *Smart electrical grids* into *Smart Energy Systems* [57].

2.2.2 Smart Energy Systems

Smart Energy System is a holistic concept for energy systems that include a focus on energy efficiency, end use savings, and sectorial integration of different systems e.g., electrical, thermal, gas, and transportation, to increase flexibility and the integration of VRE into the energy system [58]. The smart energy system concept is developed from the Smart Grids concept that focus on electric grids and how to make them more flexible. Within the literature, the concept of smart energy systems generally has two subcategories that emphasize different parts of the concept. In the first subcategory the focus is on “Smart” and aspects such as control management. In the second subcategory the focus is on “System” and the cross-sectorial approach [59]. The work presented in this thesis belongs to this second subcategory.

One characteristic of a smart energy system is, as already mentioned, the cross-sectoral aspect that means integration of different systems to achieve synergies, but also the possibility to achieve optimal solutions for both each individual sector as well as the total energy system [60]. Figure 3a) shows a traditional non-integrated fossil fuel-based energy system with parallel energy flows. This system does not make use of any cross-sector flows of e.g. waste heat or any conversion of surplus energy for use or storage in the form of other energy carriers. Figure 3b) shows an example of a smart energy system. The system is integrated by linking the electric system with the transport system for fuel synthesis and also the thermal system for heat production via heat pumps, using surplus electricity from VRE. The thermal system also provides power production from CHP for the electric system. In addition, the fuel synthesis is integrated with the heating sector by supplying excess heat from gasifiers to supply the heat demand. To increase flexibility, a TES is connected to help manage the time-wise mismatches between heat demand and supply. The level of achieved integration between different energy systems, is to some extent dependent on access to energy storages for all sectors at different system levels and for different energy carriers, i.e., electric, thermal, solid, liquid and gaseous fuels [62]. Electricity, for example, is primarily stored short-term in batteries or converted to chemical storage in the form of hydrogen or

Figure 2.3. A schematic representation of a traditional non-integrated energy system, a) and an integrated smart energy system b). Based on [61].

methanol, while fuel is stored as solid fuel or as synthesis gas after gasification [61]. The exact type of storage is not decisive, but rather the fact that energy storage will be crucial for the realization of smart energy systems. In addition, there are other aspects that must be considered for the need of a smart energy system to arise. First, the amount of VRE must be of such a quantity that power surpluses occasionally occur. Secondly, current market structures are not suitable for a multi-sector approach [58]. Tariffs and taxation of electricity are currently not designed to encourage the use of surplus electricity for the production of heat and/or gaseous fuels.

Here follow a few examples from studies investigating market incentives that could enable smart energy systems. In the literature several barriers to increased use of heat pumps and electric boilers to consume VRE surpluses has been highlighted: high electricity taxes [63], tax exemptions for biofuels that make biomass-based boilers more competitive [71], and network tariffs [63]-[73]. In [74] it is shown that with a dynamic tariff the consumption of electricity for heat production increases significantly compared to a rigid constant tariff. When the electricity consumed is produced from fossil-free renewables, this is beneficial for the decarbonization of the heating sector. The dynamic tariff directs electricity consumption to periods of low demand, thus alleviating capacity shortage problems. However, it does not steer electricity consumption to specifically target excess electricity from VRE. Reference [63] also concludes that a tariff designed to increase the use of P2H will come at the cost of reduced CHP power production due to less available heat load. This could lead to less flexible electricity generation if not considered in tariff design.

2.3 Technologies for smart energy systems

The following section provides background regarding some of the most relevant technologies that can be used to achieve smart energy systems. The focus is on the challenges that these technologies face in providing the flexibility that is expected to be needed in a smart energy system. This is also the core subject of this thesis since it deals with the link between the electricity and heating sectors. Therefore, heat and power generation technologies are focused on here. Initially the CHP technology is presented. After that the most common P2H production units is presented followed by the introduction of TES and finally some introduction to biomass-based fuel. Other technologies may of course be of greater relevance when investigating other inter-sector linkages, such as transport, gas and/or building energy demand.

2.3.1 Combined heat and power

CHP plants are generally costly investments, but the combined production of both heat and electricity results in a low net production cost [63]. This makes CHP typical base-load production units in DHSs [49]. If municipal solid waste is used as fuel, this results in even lower net production cost, as the DH operator is entitled to charge a depository fee for waste management when providing a waste management service for the municipalities [52]. Also, various types of biomass-based residues from the wood and pulp industry are relatively cheap fuels that are common in CHP plants. More expensive fuels are refined biomass fuels, i.e. pellets and fossil fuels and are also used to some extent [65].

The choice of fuel also affects other aspects of the performance of a cogeneration plant. Different types of fuel vary in e.g. ash content, moisture and/or impurities, which requires specific adjustments of the whole plant. Therefore, furnace, fuel feed and flue gas management, are different in different plants to optimize combustion and production [66]. This also implies that once a cogeneration plant has been built, it has been optimized for a particular type of fuel, and cannot therefore easily be changed to a radically different type of fuel [67]. This is important to keep in mind when studying the potential for power balancing from CHP boilers in the DH sector. Converting a CHP plant to a different fuel type can, however, be done, and has been done, but it is generally expensive [68].

Some relevant flexibility parameters when examining the potential balancing power production from a CHP plant are given in Table 2.2. The *start-up time* refers to the time it takes for the boiler to reach 90 % of the rated thermal output from cold start. Here, a cold start is defined as the start-up of a plant more than 48 hours after the plant was shut down [35]. The start-up time is relevant at times when the electricity production from VRE generation decreases significantly. The *power-to-heat ratio* or α -value is a measure of the amount of electricity produced in relation to the amount of heat produced. If the α -value is low, it means that small amounts of electricity are produced to meet an electricity balancing need and a large amount of heat is produced to meet the heat demand [47]. The *ramp rate* is a measure of how fast the CHP plant can change the power output per time unit. For ease of comparison, it is conventionally expressed as a relative per-minute change to the nominal electricity production capacity [% P_n /min] [69]. This parameter, as well as the start-up time, is important in the event of a power shortage. Finally, the *minimum load* is a parameter for the lowest possible load at which the CHP unit can operate [70]. This can be considered as a standby level, where the CHP plant is ready to increase production if needed. During periods of high variation in electricity production from the VRE, the time between electricity deficits may be too short for a complete shutdown of the unit, in which case the unit can be operated at minimum load. Each start-up of a CHP plant is costly due to

inefficient fuel use [70]. Both start-up and ramp-up cause thermal expansions in the equipment that over time cause wear and tear [41]. A cogeneration plant may need to be partially adjusted or retrofitted to cope with these thermal stresses [78], [35].

As shown in Table 2.2, the key flexibility parameters vary between different types of production plants, but it is important to remember that these parameters vary even if the same type of fuel is used depending on the furnace burner and auxiliary equipment used. These differ depending on the fuel used, the type of burner and other auxiliary equipment. The values given in the table are aggregated representative values.

Table 2.2. *Key flexibility parameters of thermal power plants. CP means condensing power, i.e., not connected to a DHS. Based on data retrieved from [35], [76] – [79].*

Fuel	Start-up [h]	α [-]	Ramp rate [%P _n /min]	Min. load [%P _n]
Municipal solid waste, CHP	12	0.2	2	0.35
Biomass wood waste, CHP	3	0.4-0.6	4	0.15-0.25
Lignite, CP plant	8-10	N/A	1-2	0.5-0.6

In Sweden there are about 500 DHSs. In 2019, 135 of these contained CHP plants, 35 of which were waste incineration plants [80]. The total installed electrical capacity was 3,964 MW_{el} with a net production of 8,924 GWh_{el} which corresponded to approximately 7% of the annual electricity demand [75].

2.3.2 Power-to-heat

Power-to-heat refers to technologies that use electricity to produce heat. Such technologies include electric resistive heaters (radiators, underfloor heating), domestic hot water heaters, compression-driven heat pumps and electric resistive boilers. The first two technologies are typically at end-user level, which is also the case for small-scale heat pumps, and are in focus in studies on demand side management in smart energy systems as in [81].

Compression-driven heat pumps and electric resistive boilers can be of large scale and used for heat production in a DHSs. In Sweden, these technologies are well established since the 1980s and represents a combined electricity consumption capacity of 1.6 GW_{el} [53], [82]. There are fundamental differences between heat pumps and electric boilers in terms of how the heat is produced. This is also important for their applicability in smart energy systems. For example, an electric boiler has a nearly instantaneous response, while a heat pump has a lead time before it is fully operational [83]. This means, for example, that if the technologies are to help in controlling the grid

frequency, they are suitable for different segments of the reserve capacity markets because of the difference in response time. In addition, there is a significant difference in investment cost between these two technologies with heat pumps being more expensive than electric boilers [84]. On the other hand, heat pumps are more efficient than electric boilers and can therefore produce more heat at a lower cost. In that sense, heat pumps have the characteristics of a base-load technology – high investment costs and low operational costs [85]. Electric boilers are best suited as a technology for fast frequency restoration service in the reserve capacity market and as peak load units to consume high power surplus peak [85].

2.3.3 Thermal energy storage

Thermal energy storages can be categorized based on physical properties: Chemical, Latent, or Sensible. *Chemical TES* use the chemical reactivity of different medium to store heat. Thermal energy is stored without degradation [86]. Under required conditions, i.e., pressure and/or moisture, a reaction occur and heat is released [87]. The benefits with chemical TES are high energy density and no losses during storage. However, these storages are still cost-intensive and further development is needed for the technologies to be fully commercialized [88].

Latent TES use the latent heat required for a storage medium to change state of phase from solid to liquid. When charging or discharging a latent TES the medium does not change in temperature, it changes state of phase which requires significant amounts of energy [89]. It is often referred to as phase change materials, PCM. There are many different materials that can be used for latent TES [90]. They span over a large range of different temperatures which makes them suitable for different purposes. Typical difficulties with various latent storage materials are degradation over repeated cycling, poor thermal conductivity and containment due to toxicity or corrosiveness [91]. Nevertheless, the energy density of latent heat material is 50 – 100 times higher than the thermal storage capacity of sensible materials, giving compact storage solutions [92].

Sensible TES is the most mature storage technology available for storing heat [93]. When charging and discharging a sensible TES the storage medium change in temperature by sensible heating/cooling. The amount of energy that can be stored via sensible heating is described as

$$Q_{stored} = c_V \times \Delta T \times V \quad (2.1)$$

where c_V is the volumetric heat capacity of the medium in (J/m³ K), ΔT is the change in temperature of the medium in K, and V is the volume of the medium in m³ [94]. Sensible TESs are typically divided into two subcategories depending on the phase of the storage medium – liquid or solid. The most common

liquid storage medium is water, but the choice of medium depends on the purpose of the storage [95]. For storing temperatures above 100°C water needs to be pressurized to avoid boiling and with high enough temperatures this becomes difficult. Thus, other mediums are available such as thermal oils, molten salts, or liquid metals [92]. Within DHSs the storing temperature is typically below 95°C. Common storage techniques are shown in table 2.3 where the most commonly applied technique is the insulated steel tank. Tanks are a well-established technology that, in different scales, are used to manage daily heat demand variations in DHSs [48] as well as domestically for hot tap water systems.

For smart energy systems, the use of TESs will be slightly different than the typical current use of a TES within DHSs. As mentioned, TES is currently typically used to manage daily heat demand variations [48]. However, during high electricity prices the CHP unit can generate power even if the current heat demand is low and store heat in a TES. Thereafter, the heat demand can be supplied with stored heat when the thermal capacity of the CHP unit is not sufficient to cover the heat demand. For this purpose, tanks are very beneficial. In 2016 there were approximately 900,000 m³ of tank TESs installed in Sweden [96]. However, the currently used operational strategy is based on cost minimizing the heat production to supply the heat demand [46]. If instead, a DHS would be supposed to operate to primarily aid in power balancing, the co-produced heat will not necessarily meet the current heat demand level. There might be significant temporal mismatches between heat supply and demand, hence a TES must be able to store high capacities to accommodate peak production and demand as well as have large storing capacity to cover long temporal shifts between production and demand [97].

Table 2.3. *The most common sensible storage technologies. The +, 0, and - indicates beneficial, moderate or poor performance for the given property. Synthesis based on [93], [98], [99], [100], [101], [102], [103].*

TES	Tank	Cavern	Ground pit	Aquifer	Bore hole	Packed bed
Energy density	+	+	0	-	-	0
Cycling	Diurnal	+	+	0	-	+
	Seasonal	-	+	0	+	-
Power capacity	0	+	+	-	-	+
Energy capacity	-	+	+	0	0	-
Response	+	+	+	-	-	+
Low loss	+	+	+	0	0	+
Low cost	0	-	+	+	+	0

As said before, energy storages are expected to be increasingly needed to balance VRE in smart energy systems. Sensible TES using water as storage medium can potentially have economic advantages to do this [104].

2.3.4 Biomass demand

As mentioned in the introduction, there is currently an overarching ambition to combat climate change in the global community, and the use of biomass is important in this context. Biomass is biogenic carbon and thus part of the short-term carbon cycle based on photosynthesis, respiration and decomposition (70 – 100 years in sequestration time). Previous studies have pointed out the differences in access to biomass in different parts of the world [105] and the danger of overexploitation of biomass (deforestation, biodiversity, land-use change) [106]. Also, there is competition for the use of biomass since it can be used for many purposes, e.g., construction material, pulp, petrochemical replacements, textiles, and fuel for transportation [107]. By replacing fossil fuels with biomass, emissions are shifted from the long-term to the short-term carbon cycle. This does not, however, mean that biomass alone is a possible way to eliminate fossil fuel use globally. Beside the competing use of biomass, several other factors such as competing land use, availability, and biodiversity affects the quantities of biomass available for fossil fuel substitution [108]. It has been suggested that biomass only should be considered a means to an end for reaching a fully electrified society based on 100% renewable energy [61]. A way to replace biomass used for heat production is to use P2H. In this matter, heat pumps are more efficient than electric boilers. P2H can partly reduce the demand on biomass. However, the use of biomass-fired CHP plants for power balancing production will still maintain some demand for biomass.

2.4 Research gaps

The following research gaps were identified when reviewing the scientific literature. All these identified gaps are addressed in this thesis, but to varying extent.

- *Power balancing production strategies* in the heating sector is merely considered when it comes to P2H. Possible power balancing services that can be offered by DHSs have only been investigated on rudimentary level. Peak electricity demand occurs at few occasions per year and typically require high capacity. It has not been fully investigated if the heating sector is best suited to supply peak electricity demand and/or if it should offer a base electricity production/consumption that follows the electricity demand.
- *Market barriers* for the coupling of the electrical and thermal energy systems have been investigated, but mainly focused on obstacles that prevent a coupling via P2H due to tariffs, taxes, and grid fees. It has been suggested that DH utilities should offer P2H capacities on the

electricity reserve capacity market, but it has neither been fully investigated how such a market structure would look like nor what kind of compensations to DHSs for providing power balancing production this would require.

- *Heat production from P2H and CHP units* in smart energy systems will be operated in an unconventional way. This is a crucial difference and could affect the potential for power balancing services. It has not been thoroughly investigated how heat pumps and CHP should be combined in different DHSs where the focus is to enhance the energy system flexibility.
- *Solar and wind power have different variability* and thus require different flexibility from the energy sectors. How the relative shares of PV and wind power, respectively, affects power balancing production from the heating sector has not been investigated in the literature.
- *P2H as means to decarbonize the heating sector* and offer negative power balance to the electricity grid. In the literature there are no studies that investigate to what extent synergy effects from P2H when used in a smart energy system, operated to provide power balancing services, depends on the distribution between PRL and NRL. It has not been investigated if there is a threshold where such a synergy effect no longer can be detected or if P2H always will contribute with both decarbonization and negative power balance. And furthermore, it has not been fully investigated if there is a point where P2H may outcompete the positive power balance production from CHP units.
- *The size of the TES is limiting the operational strategy* of it. Large enough the TES can be operated on seasonal basis and replace costly peak load units, but with smaller dimensions it must be operated differently. In the literature there are no studies investigating how this affects the possible power balancing service. It has not been investigated if seasonal operation of the TES more likely can offer needed flexibility to balance positive and negative peak electricity demand, or if both short term and seasonal operation are equally efficient as flexible loads to promote power balancing.

3 Method

This chapter presents the methods and data used in this thesis. The chapter starts with an overview of studied system components and systems interaction in Section 3.1. In Section 3.2, the model for the electricity balancing demand used in the studies is described. Section 3.3 presents the energy balances based on which the technologies are modelled, and in Section 3.4 the scenarios studied are described. The methods used for assessing fuel use is given in Section 3.5 and, finally, in Section 3.6 methods for economic assessment are described.

3.1 The studied energy systems

In general, it can be said that the studied aspects of the systems are the interaction between the thermal and the electrical energy systems and the capacity to reduce the VRE-induced power net-load variability. All systems presented in the appended Papers contain production units (CHP and/or heat pumps), that either produce or consume electricity in combination with production of heat. Furthermore, different types of large-scale TESs are modelled in the studies. All components are not included in all system, partly because they are studied at different system levels. This is further explained in Section 3.4. However, all studies include the restriction that CHP and heat pumps must not, on annual basis, produce more heat than the system heat load, i.e. no heat is allowed to be intentionally wasted. Energy flows and relationships between components and other energy systems included in the studies are shown schematically in Figure 3.1. The Roman numbers refer to the respective studies/Papers in which the components are included. The grey boxes represent supply of VRE to the electrical transmission system (yellow lines). White boxes represent controllable devices that either produce electricity (CHP) or consume electricity (heat pumps) electricity. These units produce heat that is delivered to the district heating network (red lines), to which heat-storing units (TES) also is connected. The EES-box in Figure 3.1 represents an electric energy storage (EES), i.e., a flow-battery. End-users are represented by the black boxes and they consume both electricity and heat. Industrial and commercial actors are represented by the “Ind/com”-box. These are potentially both heat consumers and heat suppliers. For all energy flows, the arrows show the

Figure 3.1. The energy flows, components and their correlation with respectively energy transmission network of the systems that are studied in this thesis. Abbreviations: BAPV = building applied photovoltaics, SfB = single family buildings, MfB = multifamily buildings, Ind/com = industrial and commercial buildings, DCN = district cooling network, HP and hp = LARGE- and small-scale heat pumps.

direction of the flow (i.e. an arrow out from a unit indicates production and an arrow in to a unit indicates consumption). Arrows in both directions indicate a storage, combined producer and consumer, or bi-directional flows as for import/export of electricity. The dotted lines and symbols are not active components of the system studies in this thesis, but represent either important system boundaries (e.g. import/export), alternative costs (e.g. Thermal power in Paper II), or relevant system expansions and/or alternative thermal systems (cooling district network) that are addressed in the discussion.

The control signal for the simulations in the studies is the electricity balancing demand which is described in Section 3.2. This signal initiates production in CHP units or large-scale heat pumps. If the electricity balancing demand is positive, there is a deficit of VRE and the CHP will co-produce electricity and heat. The heat is delivered to the district heating network and any surplus heat is stored in the thermal storage. If the electricity balancing demand is negative, there is a surplus of VRE and the heat pumps consume electricity. The heat produced from these is managed in the same way as heat from CHP. If the electricity balancing demand is zero, neither CHP nor heat pumps are producing heat. In that case, heat demand is supplied by stored heat from TESs. Models and energy balances for the units included in the calculations/simulations are described in Section 3.3.

For all studies, a full year is simulated with an hourly time-resolution. Simulations have been made in MATLAB, SIMULINK and HEAT3. In addition,

extensive pre- and post-processing of the data has been done in Excel as most of the input data is available as Excel spreadsheets.

3.2 Modelling the electricity balancing demand

As described in Section 2.1.1, electricity production and consumption need to be momentarily balanced. In Section 2.1.2, the maintenance of this balance is described. In Papers I – IV it is assumed that the systems studied are active on the day-ahead market primarily. In Paper V, systems that are acting on the reserve capacity market is studied. The work presented in this thesis investigates the power balancing potential in the heating sector mainly from a technical point of view. This means that even though DH utilities are active on one or several electricity markets, the studies do not include simulations of the actual trading on the markets. This is because of that the primary focus in this thesis is the technical potential of DHSs to provide power balancing services. However, the understanding of the functions of power markets is important for the analyses of these potentials. In order to illustrate a capacity market control-signal for electricity production and consumption, an electricity balancing demand profile was derived for the Swedish power system with large shares of VRE. The derived demand does not include dispatchable electricity generators, such as hydro or thermal power generation. This means that the electricity balancing demand used in the work presented here is a theoretical intermediate electricity demand. The main benefits are that such a theoretical demand clearly exemplifies the potential imbalances and when in time positive and/or negative power balance production would be most required.

In Paper I and II, the systems studied are in local and small residential areas and thus, the focus is on the local power balance. However, since the low voltage grid in the residential area is connected to upstream electric network, there will be effects from power imbalances in the upstream network affecting the local grid. The *electricity balance demand model, M1*, used in these two Papers are different than in the other Papers. The local electricity balancing demand for each timestep i is expressed as

$$P_{bal}^{el}(i) = P_{LD}^{el}(i) + C_1 P_{bal}^{el*}(i) - P_{BAPV}^{el}(i) \quad (3.1)$$

where P_{LD}^{el} is the local electricity demand, C_1 is a scaling factor for the national electricity balancing demand, P_{bal}^{el*} , P_{BAPV}^{el} is the local building applied PV (BAPV) electricity production. P_{bal}^{el*} is the difference between the national electricity demand, P_{ND}^{el} , and the produced VRE, P_{VRE}^{el} , on national level, thus

$$P_{bal}^{el*}(i) = P_{ND}^{el}(i) - P_{VRE}^{el}(i). \quad (3.2)$$

In Paper I P_{bal}^{el} and P_{bal}^{el*} include parameters that are used to increase the amount of BAPV and reduce the amount of nuclear power in the national power production, this also is used for Paper II.

The scaling factor C_1 in (3.1) is used to get a proportional representation of the P_{bal}^{el*} on local level and is defined as the ratio between local and national electricity demand, thus described as

$$C_1 = \frac{\sum_i P_{LD}^{el}(i)}{\sum_i P_{ND}^{el}(i)}. \quad (3.3)$$

P_{VRE}^{el} in (3.2) represents the aggregated national production from wind, P_W^{el} , and solar power, P_{PV}^{el} , and is defined as

$$P_{VRE}^{el}(i) = C_2 P_W^{el}(i) + C_3 P_{PV}^{el}(i). \quad (3.4)$$

Production from wind and solar power are scaled by the factors C_2 and C_3 to represent a production corresponding to 60% and 10%, respectively, of the national electricity demand. These two scaling factors are defined as

$$C_2 = 0.6 \frac{\sum_i P_{ND}^{el}(i)}{\sum_i P_W^{el}(i)}, \quad (3.5)$$

and

$$C_3 = 0.1 \frac{\sum_i P_{ND}^{el}(i)}{\sum_i P_{PV}^{el}(i)}. \quad (3.6)$$

In Papers III – V, simulations are applied on a higher system level and for this a second *electricity balance demand model*, M2, was derived. The major difference between M1 and M2 is that M2 is based on aggregated production and consumption data for each electricity price area in Sweden. Hence, M2 does neither contain specific consumption data for a local area nor electricity production from BAPV, as these are both represented in the aggregated data. Furthermore, another significant difference is that M2 considers transmission capacity limitations between the different electricity price areas. For every time step i , the studied system responds to an electricity balancing demand level, $P_{bal}^{SE_j}$, in electricity price area j in Sweden. This is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} P_{bal}^{SE_j}(i) &= P_{PRL}^{SE_j}(i) + P_{NRL}^{SE_k}(i) \quad \{j, k = 1, 2, 3, 4 \quad j \neq k\} \\ \text{iff } P_{NRL}^{SE_k}(i) &\leq T_{cap}^{j,k}(i) \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

where $T_{cap}^{j,k}$ is the transmission line capacity from electricity price area SE_j to area SE_k . Electricity transmission capacities between areas are considered in the model. $P_{NRL}^{SE_k}$ is the negative residual load (excess electricity) in area k , and $P_{PRL}^{SE_j}$ is the positive residual load (remaining electricity demand) in area j . These two loads are given by

$$P_{PRL}^{SE_j}(i) = \begin{cases} P_L^{SE_j}(i) - P_{VRE}^{SE_j}(i), & \text{iff } > 0 \\ 0, & \text{iff } \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad \{j = 1, 2, 3, 4\} \quad (3.8)$$

and

$$P_{NRL}^{SE_j}(i) = \begin{cases} P_L^{SE_j}(i) - P_{VRE}^{SE_j}(i), & \text{iff } < 0 \\ 0, & \text{iff } \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad \{j = 1, 2, 3, 4\}. \quad (3.9)$$

$P_L^{SE_j}$ is the electricity consumption per hour i in the electricity price area j in Sweden. $P_{VRE}^{SE_j}$ is the electricity production from wind and solar power in area j as defined in (3.4). The priority of transmitting any NRL in one region to supply an existing PRL in another region follows a predetermined order based on annual figures for highest production, $T_{cap}^{export} = [SE_2 \ SE_1 \ SE_3 \ SE_4]$, respective highest demand, $T_{cap}^{import} = [SE_3 \ SE_4 \ SE_2 \ SE_1]$, in all regions. This means that, for every time step, if there is an NRL in region SE_2 this will be transmitted to the first region, where there is a PRL, following the predetermined order in T_{cap}^{import} . If there is no NRL in SE_2 , or all has been fully transmitted, the next region in T_{cap}^{export} starts to transmit NRL and so forth until either all NRL has been transmitted in all regions up till the limit of the transmission line capacities, or until all PRL is fully supplied. In Paper V, the transmission capacities are assumed to be sufficiently expanded to cover required transmission demand. Hence, for Paper V, the ‘if and only if’ condition in (3.7) is not valid.

Figure 3.2 a) shows how the local electricity demand, P_{LD}^{el} , is added with the national electricity balancing demand, P_{bal}^{el} , and subtracted with the local BAPV electricity production, P_{BAPV}^{el} , resulting in the electricity balancing demand, P_{bal}^{el} , used as control signal for the system simulations in Paper I and II. Figure 3.2 b) shows how the aggregated electricity demand for electricity price area 3, P_L^{SE3} , is subtracted with the VRE generation from the same area, P_{VRE}^{SE3} , resulting in $P_{residual}^{SE3}$. After transmission to and from other electricity price areas this intermediate residual profile results in the electricity balancing demand, P_{bal}^{SE3} , used as control signal for Papers III – V.

Figure 3.2. Figure a) show the constituent parts of the electricity balancing demand, P_{bal}^{el} , used in Papers I and II. Figure b) shows ditto for Papers III - V.

3.3 Simulation approaches

For all the appended studies, rule-based algorithms are used that are based on energy balances and physical constraints. The algorithms respond to the control signal, P_{bal}^{el} , by simulating production and/or consumption of electricity in designated facilities. Also, the co-produced heat is simulated and how this heat is stored and/or used to supply the heat demand of the DHS. The algorithm used in Paper I and II has an overarching goal of using the TES and/or the EES to supply the annual thermal or electrical peak demands. In the other Papers there is no such seasonal peak shaving strategy for the operation of the TES. In all Papers, algorithms prioritize consumption of NRL in heat pumps, when possible. Furthermore, for all studies the PRL activates the operation of a CHP unit to co-produce electricity and heat. No heat is allowed to be wasted.

3.3.1 Energy balances

The heat demand is a boundary condition in all appended Papers. This means that the produced heat must be used and the annual heat demand sets the limit for production in CHP and/or heat pumps. For every time-step i , the heat demand, P_{HD}^{th} , is supplied according to

$$P_{HD}^{th}(i) = \sum_n^N P_{CHP_n}^{th}(i) + \sum_k^K P_{HoB_k}^{th}(i) + P_{HP}^{th}(i) + P_{TES}^{th}(i). \quad (3.10)$$

$P_{CHP_n}^{th}$ is the heat produced in CHP-plant n , and $P_{HoB_k}^{th}$ is heat produced in heat-only boiler k , P_{HP}^{th} is heat produced in heat pumps, and P_{TES}^{th} is heat discharged from TES. For as long as the heat demand is supplied, the heat production from technologies are operated to also reduce an electricity balancing demand, which contribute to a resulting net electricity demand, P_{net}^{el} , as

$$P_{net}^{el}(i) = P_{bal}^{el}(i) + P_{HP}^{el}(i) + P_{ch}^{el}(i) - P_{dc}^{el}(i) - \sum_n^N P_{CHP_n}^{el}(i). \quad (3.11)$$

Here P_{bal}^{el} equals the electricity balancing demand, i.e., control signal of respective study as defined in (3.1) or (3.7). $P_{CHP_n}^{el}$ is the produced electricity in CHP-plant n , and P_{dc}^{el} electricity discharged from EES. P_{HP}^{el} is electricity consumed in heat pumps, and P_{ch}^{el} is electricity used to charge the EES.

The TES acts as a flexible load that enables operation of CHP units and heat pumps to produce more heat than the present heat demand level as long as there is storage capacity available in the TES. The energy balance of the TES is defined as

$$P_{TES}^{th}(i) = P_{TES}^{th}(i-1) + P_{in}^{th}(i) - P_{out}^{th}(i) - P_{loss}^{th}(i). \quad (3.12)$$

P_{loss}^{th} represent the losses in the TES and the calculation of these losses depend on the type of storage (see Section 3.4.3). The surplus heat supplied to the TES, P_{in}^{th} , is described as

$$P_{in}^{th}(i) = \sum_n^N P_{CHP_n}^{th}(i) + P_{HP}^{th}(i) - P_{HD}^{th}(i) \quad (3.13)$$

and heat discharged from the storage to supply the heat demand is

$$P_{out}^{th}(i) = P_{HD}^{th}(i) - \sum_n^N P_{CHP_n}^{th}(i) - P_{HP}^{th}(i). \quad (3.14)$$

Available capacity in the TES is directly affected by the use of the TES which in turn depends on the operational strategy of the TES. In this thesis, three different strategies have been applied. In Papers I and II the operation of the TES uses a *Seasonal peak shave*-strategy, which means that the TES is iteratively in the algorithm dimensioned to have enough capacity to cover 50% of the thermal peak demand. At the same time, the producing units needs to produce sufficient amounts of heat to cover the heat demand and the losses in the TES during seasonal storing. This also means that the dimensioning of the CHP unit's capacity can be reduced. The strategy prioritizes consumption of NRL which requires a large capacity in heat pumps. In Papers III and IV, a different operational strategy of the TES is applied, i.e., a *Rigid* strategy, which omits the seasonal peak shaving aspect. In this *Rigid* strategy the TES mainly adds flexibility to the system without requirements for other production technologies to be dimensioned to match the TES capacity. This means that production capacities can be higher than what is conventional since these can be dimensioned for power balancing production. Paper V applies a third operational strategy for the TES, namely the *Naïve* strategy. This means that the stored heat is prioritized to be used if the heat demand level at hour i is

higher than at hour $i - 1$. If the stored heat is insufficient the currently active production unit increase the rate of production, if possible. Otherwise a new production technology is activated for production of heat. The major difference with this strategy compared to the previous two strategies is that the stored heat is not allowed to replace heat from other active heat production, i.e., “forcing” a producing unit to ramp down.

3.3.2 Summary of data and algorithms

Table 3.1 provides an overview of the type of data used in the different studies and Table 3.2 presents overall production algorithms used in each study. Details are given in the respective section referred to.

Table 3.1. *Data and type used in the Papers of this thesis.*

Data	Section	Paper					
		I	II	III	IV	V	
Heat demand	<i>Simulated</i>	3.8.1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Thermal production capacities	<i>Public data</i>	3.8.1			✓		
	<i>Assumed capacities</i>		✓	✓		✓	✓
BAPV	<i>Simulated</i>	3.8.2	✓	✓			
VRE production, national	<i>Public data</i>	3.8.2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Transmission constraints	<i>Public data</i>	3.8.2			✓	✓	
	<i>Assumed capacities</i>		✓	✓			✓
Power consumption	<i>Public data</i>	3.8.2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	<i>Simulated</i>		✓	✓			
Economic data		3.8.3		✓			✓
Outdoor temperature	<i>Public data</i>		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 3.2. *Algorithmic models applied in each of the studies in the thesis.*

Algorithmic model	Section	Paper					
		I	II	III	IV	V	
TES volume	<i>Fixed</i>	3.4.3				✓	
	<i>Dynamic</i>		✓	✓	✓		✓
Storage strategy	<i>Naïve</i>	3.3.1					✓
	<i>Rigid</i>				✓	✓	
	<i>Seasonal peak shave</i>		✓	✓			
CHP capacity	<i>Fixed</i>	3.4.2	✓	✓	✓		✓
	<i>Min net load variability</i>					✓	
Heat pump capacity	<i>Maximized</i>	3.4.1	✓	✓	✓		
	<i>Discrete steps</i>						✓
	<i>Min net load variability</i>					✓	
Transmission limit		3.2			✓	✓	
Electricity balancing demand	<i>M1</i>	3.2	✓	✓			
	<i>M2</i>				✓	✓	✓

3.4 Technologies for power balancing and heat production

The different technologies simulated in the appended Papers are modelled on a high system level. This means that there have been no considerations of detailed components, but all technologies are considered as separate systems that can be described with efficiencies, rate of change in production, and energy balances.

3.4.1 Power-to-Heat

In all studies, P2H is represented by large-scale central heat pumps, except for Paper II which also includes small-scale air-to-air heat pumps at the end users.

The large-scale heat pumps are modelled by the coefficient of performance (COP) which is defined as

$$COP = \eta_{carnot} \frac{T_H}{T_H - T_C} \quad (3.13)$$

where η_{carnot} is the efficiency of the system compared to the ideal Carnot process, for large-scale systems typically around 0.65 [109]. T_H is the temperature at the heat sink (hot side) and T_C is the temperature at the source (cold side), both in K. The relation between electricity consumption in the heat pumps, P_{HP}^{el} , and heat production, P_{HP}^{th} , is defined by using the COP as

$$P_{HP}^{el} = P_{HP}^{th} / COP. \quad (3.14)$$

In Paper II, small-scale air-to-air heat pumps are simulated with a model based on laboratory test data from the Swedish Energy Agency [110] and an empirically derived formula presented in [111]. This formula includes factors related to the internal and mechanical efficiencies of the compressor, as well as the Carnot efficiency and electromotor efficiency of the process and using the reported data from [110] the following equation was derived to estimate the COP of actual air-to-air heat pumps

$$COP_{air} = 1.58 + 0.082 \left(\frac{T_H}{T_H - T_C} \right). \quad (3.15)$$

3.4.2 Combined Heat and Power (CHP)

In Table 2.2, key flexibility parameters for CHP units were given. These are applied for CHP units performing power balancing production in all the studies presented in this thesis. The start-up time for a CHP unit performing a cold start is defined as

$$P_{CHP}^{th} = f \times P_{CHP}^{nom} \times \frac{t}{\tau}, \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, \tau, \quad (3.16)$$

where f is a value between 0 and 1 representing the fraction of nominal thermal capacity, P_{CHP}^{nom} , to reach, $f = 1$ when operated at maximum capacity. τ is the total start-up time in h, and t is time in hours that has passed after start up.

The relation between thermal and electrical production is modelled using the conventional power-to-heat ratio, i.e., the α -value accordingly

$$\alpha = \frac{P_{CHP}^{el}}{P_{CHP}^{th}}. \quad (3.17)$$

When assuming an ideal steam-turbine cogeneration plant, the relation between the boiler thermal output, P_{CHP}^{boiler} , is the sum of electrical power and process heat output [112] and can be expressed as

$$P_{CHP}^{boiler} = P_{CHP}^{el} + P_{CHP}^{th}. \quad (3.18)$$

Combining (3.17) and (3.18) allows expressions of the electrical power and process heat output as

$$P_{CHP}^{th} = \frac{P_{CHP}^{boiler}}{\alpha + 1} \quad (3.19)$$

and

$$P_{CHP}^{el} = \frac{P_{CHP}^{boiler}}{(1/\alpha) + 1}, \quad (3.20)$$

which are used in Paper IV. The ramp rate, φ , is expressed as the time derivative of the power output divided by the nominal electrical power of the generator, P_{gen}^{nom} , as

$$\varphi = \frac{dP_{CHP}^{el}/dt}{P_{gen}^{nom}} \times T \times 100, \quad (3.21)$$

where t is in seconds and T is seconds per minute. However, with simulations using averaged values per hour this formula becomes a constant used to control that increase in production not exceeds the nominal power output or the rated ramping speed. Finally, the minimum load is expressed as a set share, ζ , of the rated boiler output:

$$P_{CHP}^{min} = \zeta \times P_{CHP}^{boiler}. \quad (3.22)$$

CHP units that act as part of a base load production, i.e., waste incineration plants, or as part of a “Business-as-usual” reference case, are modelled slightly different. The difference is that they are simulated to follow a heat demand

and thus they are neither assumed to ramp the production excessively (3.21) nor to operate at minimum load (3.22).

3.4.3 Thermal Energy Storage

There are four different models used for simulating the operation of a TES in the appended Papers (see Figure 3.3). In Papers I and II, the TES (a) is simulated as a buried cylindrical tank, uniformly insulated where a mathematical model developed by the Swedish Built Environment Research Council [94] is used to calculate the thermal losses. In Paper III, the TES (b) is simulated as a ground pit TES. The model used to simulate the thermal losses in this case is based on Fourier's law on heat conduction implemented with operational data from a pit TES in Dronninglund in Denmark [113]. In Papers IV and V, the TESs are simulated as rock caverns. The TESs in Paper IV (c) are of fixed sizes and the losses from these TESs are simulated with an averaged thermal loss over one year. In Paper V, the sizes of the TESs are iteratively derived and thus the thermal losses from the rock cavern (d) are instead simulated using formulas from [94].

For the thermal loss in TES (c) the software Heat3 was used [114]. It is a software for 3D transient and steady-state heat conduction. The partial differential heat equation in three dimensions for the temperature $T(x,y,z,t)$ is expressed numerically by discrete approximation in a Cartesian mesh. This allows transient and steady-state problems to be solved with the method of explicit forward differences (for details the reader is referred to [115]). The software is validated according to the standard EN ISO 10211. True equilibrium takes long time (see Figure 3.4) and is not easily determined. According to the simulation in Heat3 an equilibrium with the surrounding rock could be expected after some 25 years of operation. A semi-equilibrium, when the losses are reduced less than 1% compared to previous year, occurs after some 14 years of operation. After 6 years of operation the losses are reduced with less than 5% compared to previous year.

To assess performance of the storages, they will be evaluated with respect to relative losses, i.e., the annual losses relative annual amount of heat charged to the TES, but also the energy efficiency defined as

Figure 3.3. Different types of TES simulated in the appended Papers. a) is used in Paper I and II, b) is used in Paper III, c) and d) is used in Paper IV and V respectively.

$$\eta_E = \frac{\sum_i P_{out}^{th}(i)}{\sum_i P_{in}^{th}(i)}. \quad (3.23)$$

Here P_{out}^{th} and P_{in}^{th} are heat charged and discharged to the TES as described in 3.13 and 3.14, respectively. The degree of utilization indicates to what extent the TES is used relative its capacity and is defined as

$$\eta_U = \frac{\sum_i P_{out}^{th}(i)}{P_{TES}^{cap}}. \quad (3.24)$$

Where P_{TES}^{cap} is defined according to (2.1).

Figure 3.4. Transient heat flow out from rock caverns simulated in Heat3.

3.5 Studied system configurations

Table 3.3 shows the system levels studied and the aspects covered by the research questions in the appended Papers. Figure 3.5 shows the systems simulated in order to answer the research questions. In Figure 3.5, the first row represents Paper I and II, the second row represents Paper III, and the third and fourth row represents Papers IV and V. The maps over Sweden, to the left in the Figure, show geographical coverage of the studied systems. For Paper IV, the map indicates the amount of systems in each region. In the flowcharts, the electric networks are represented by yellow lines and the thermal network by orange lines. In II-C, however, there is no DH network included, so for this case the orange lines represent domestic distribution systems. For the electric network, the upstream grid is connected bi-directionally and marked with an acronym. The acronym indicates if the P_{bal} is represented as an aggregated demand for the entire Sweden, e.g., ‘SE’, or with respect taken to transmission capacity limits between regions, e.g., ‘//SE3//’.

For Paper I and II, the same local community of 111 single-family homes is studied, while in Paper III, all DHSs in electricity price area SE3 are studied

Table 3.3. Matrix illustrating how the appended Papers relate to the research questions put forth in the aim of this thesis.

		System level →		
		Local	District	Aggregated
Research question ↓	Power balancing	I, II	IV	III, V
	Heat production	I, II	IV	III, V
	Heat storage	I, II	IV	III, V
	Fuel demand	I, II	IV	III, V
	Economic	II		V

in an aggregated form. In Paper IV, a DHS is studied on city-level for different electricity price areas and aggregated to national level. Paper V simulates three different configurations of DHSs with P2H capacities, i.e., heat pumps, active on the reserve capacity market, for one city in SE4.

In all studies, two different production strategies are used. The first strategy follows the heat demand, typical for how DHSs are currently operated – this is referred to as the ‘Heat Strategy’ and constitutes the reference case. The second strategy is, for DHSs, a theoretical production strategy where CHP units and heat pumps are operated to supply the electricity balancing demand, as described in Section 3.2. This is referred to as the ‘Electricity Strategy’. The systems studied in Paper V, however, applies only the ‘Heat Strategy’ for the operation of the DHS, while the P2H-capacities is operated according to the ‘Electricity Strategy’.

The power balancing supply consists of CHP electricity production to supply PRL (deficits), and of heat pump electricity consumption to reduce NRL (surpluses). The heat produced in CHP units and heat pumps is either used to supply DH demand, or stored in a TES for later use

The TES technologies, described in Section 3.4.3, vary between the systems as shown in Table 3.4, but also in terms of capacities as shown in Table 3.5. Also, the production technologies vary between the eleven studied systems as shown in Table 3.4. All systems have biomass-fired CHP except II-C and V-HoB, and all but three systems (II-B, III-ref, and II-C) have large-scale ground-source heat pumps. However, for the systems simulated in Paper V, only V-BioCHP include heat pumps in the DHS production assets. Nevertheless, all systems in Paper V do include heat pumps, but as P2H capacities operated to provide electricity balancing services. In system II-C, individual building air-to-air heat pumps are simulated at end user level. In the three systems simulated in Paper III and also system V-WtE, there is base-load heat supply from industrial waste heat recovery, IWH, and waste incineration, (waste-to-energy, WtE). These systems also contain peak heat load units in the form of heat-only boilers, HoB. System V-HoB is the only system with HoB as main heat producing technology.

« Figure 3.5. Representation of all simulated scenarios. Yellow lines are electricity networks, orange are thermal networks. Upstream electricity network is represented with a bi-directional feed. All acronyms are given in text.

Table 3.4 shows what technologies are applied in respective study and Table 3.5 shows how they differ between the studies in terms of installed nominal thermal output capacity relative the peak heat demand for respective study.

Table 3.4. All systems constituting technologies. HP is heat pumps, ES is energy storage either as thermal, TES, or electrical, EES, IWH is industrial waste heat, WtE is waste incineration (Waste-to-Energy), HoB is heat-only boiler.

Paper	System	CHP	HP	ES	IWH	WtE	HoB
I	<i>I-132</i>	✓	✓	Tank TES	–	–	–
II	<i>II-A</i>	✓	✓	Tank TES	–	–	–
	<i>II-B</i>	✓	–	Flow battery, EES	–	–	–
	<i>II-C</i>	–	✓	Flow battery, EES	–	–	–
III	<i>III-ref</i>	✓	–	–	✓	✓	✓
	<i>III-sc1</i>	✓	✓	Ground-pit TES	✓	✓	✓
	<i>III-sc2</i>	✓	✓	Ground-pit TES	✓	✓	–
IV	<i>IV-1</i>	✓	✓	Oblong cavern TES	–	–	–
	<i>IV-2</i>	✓	✓	Oblong cavern TES	–	–	–
V	<i>V-HoB</i>	–	✓	Cylindric cavern TES	–	–	✓
	<i>V-WtE</i>	✓	✓	Cylindric cavern TES	✓	✓	✓
	<i>V-BioCHP</i>	✓	✓	Cylindric cavern TES	–	–	✓

Table 3.5. Nominal thermal output relative the peak thermal demand for all systems constituting technologies for heat production. For Paper V both a reference case and a case with 40 MW_{th} P2H capacity for the reserve capacity market are shown.

Paper	System	CHP	HP	TES	IWH	WtE	HoB
I	<i>I-132</i>	0.50	1.68	1.33	–	–	–
II	<i>II-A</i>	0.50	1.68	1.33	–	–	–
	<i>II-B</i>	1.00	–	–	–	–	–
	<i>II-C</i>	–	1.00	–	–	–	–
III	<i>III-ref</i>	0.38	–	–	0.04	0.13	1.11
	<i>III-sc1</i>	0.38	0.20	2.00	0.04	0.13	1.11
	<i>III-sc2</i>	1.49	0.20	2.00	0.04	0.13	–
IV	<i>IV-1</i>	1.30	1.48	1.48	–	–	–
	<i>IV-2</i>	1.24	1.61	1.61	–	–	–
V	<i>V-HoB ref</i>	–	–	–	–	–	1.01
	<i>V-HoB 40</i>	–	0.35	0.49	–	–	1.01
	<i>V-WtE ref</i>	0.35	–	0.06	0.10	0.35	0.35
	<i>V-WtE 40</i>	–	0.35	0.61	0.10	0.35	–
	<i>V-BioCHP ref</i>	0.49	0.20	0.04	–	–	0.49
	<i>V-BioCHP 40</i>	0.49	0.55	0.60	–	–	0.25

3.6 Fuel

In this thesis, calculations of fuel use are mainly focused on the use of biomass, i.e., no calculations are done regarding fossil fuels. In the appended studies that consider fuel use, it is assumed that wood chips are used. It has an averaged net calorific value of 2.88 GJ/m³ or 16.92 GJ/tonne [116]. The fuel consumption in heat and/or power producing units is a function of boiler energy conversion efficiency and for CHP units also mechanical efficiencies regarding turbine, generator, and auxiliary system components. Thus, the fuel use is calculated using the boiler efficiency for HoB and the total production efficiency for CHP units as

$$Q_f = \frac{\sum_i P^{th}(i) + \sum_i P^{el}(i)}{\eta_{tot}}. \quad (3.25)$$

Biomass is considered carbon neutral, but combustion of biomass still causes emissions of other GHG [117]. GHG-emissions are calculated as (CO_{2,eq}) according to

$$GHG_{bio} = Q_f \left(\phi_{CH_4} GWP_{CH_4} + \phi_{N_2O} GWP_{N_2O} \right) \quad (3.26)$$

where ϕ is the emission factor for the indexed GHG in kg/MWh and GWP is the global warming potential for the GHG indexed according to Table 3.4.

Table 3.4. Emission factors and global warming potential (GWP) for GHGs in a 100-year perspective [116], [118].

Emission factors and GWP ₁₀₀	GHG		
	CO ₂	CH ₄	N ₂ O
Emission factor ϕ [kg/MWh]	345.6	0.0396	0.0108
Global warming potential, GWP ₁₀₀ [CO _{2,eq}]	1.0	25.0	298.0

3.7 Economic assessment

Different economic aspects are investigated in two of the appended Papers (II and V). In Paper II, the economic-viability for investment and operation are investigated for three different storage-based heating solutions. In Paper V, it is investigated how DH utilities can operate P2H capacities on the reserve capacity market.

The economic performance of the systems is evaluated by the net present value (NPV), internal rate of return (IRR), profitability index (PI) [119], and the present value ratio (PVR) [120]. The NPV is the current value of the difference between all expected cash inflows and outflows over a defined time period. A negative NPV is considered as non-profitable and should, out of a

capitalisation point of view, be discarded. NPV is based on assumed cash inflows and discount rate which, of course, gives uncertainties to the assessment. It is then useful to calculate the IRR to determine required discount rate that makes the NPV equal zero. Any project for which the IRR is greater than its required discount rate (i.e., rate of return), is considered profitable. Even without a specified required rate of return, the IRR is useful to determine the expected profitability of an investment. The higher the IRR, the greater the expected revenue. Negative IRR indicates loss of investment. It can thus also be used for reducing costs of e.g., large infrastructural projects that are not expected to bring profit. When calculating the IRR, any residual economic value at the end of the defined time-period is discounted. This gives different cash flows in comparison to the NPV and can thus give somewhat contradictory results in some cases. Therefore, two complementary measures, PI and PRV, can be used. The PI is a measure of the expected profit per monetary unit invested in the project and should be greater than 1 to indicate economic viability. The PVR is a measure of the economic efficiency of the project and should be greater than zero to indicate economic viability. The PI and PVR can be used to determine which project that gives the best economic return alternatively reduces the cost the most. Projects with the same PVR are indicated to be equally efficient in capitalisation or cost reduction (assuming a similar discount rate). Typically, it is unfair to compare projects with very different magnitude of investment costs. Therefore, it is relevant to use several measures to assess the economic outcome of a project from different aspects.

NPV is defined as the current total value of a future stream of payments and is calculated according to

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} \right) - C_0. \quad (3.27)$$

C_t is the net cash inflow during the time-period t , C_0 is total initial investment cost, and r is discount rate. The IRR is calculated by setting the NPV to equal zero and solve for the discount rate,

$$0 = NPV = \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\frac{C_t}{(1+IRR)^t} \right) - C_0 \quad (3.28)$$

which then will be the IRR. The PI is the ratio between the future predicted revenues in present value, NPV, and the initial investment, and calculated as

$$PI = 1 + \frac{NPV}{C_0}. \quad (3.29)$$

PVR is the ratio of NPV and the initial investment calculated as

$$PVR = \frac{NPV}{C_0}. \quad (3.30)$$

In Paper V, a “willingness-to-pay” is defined to identify the bidding price a DH utility can accept for placing a bid on the reserve capacity market for the purchase of surplus electricity as negative power balance. If the price on the reserve capacity market is higher than the identified bidding price, it is not economically feasible for the DH utility to participate. A production baseline is used for comparison of production cost for every level l of P2H capacity. This baseline production has no P2H capacity active on the reserve market. Total production cost, C_{tot} , per level l is given by

$$C_{tot}^l = \sum_k c \times Q_f^k, \quad (3.31)$$

Where c is the net cost for heat production with fuel Q_f and technology k . The specific values can be found in the appended Paper V. By comparison with the baseline cost for respective case, a “willingness-to-pay”, i.e., “the highest average bid-price to remain profitable”, can be determined. This is estimated by calculating an average cost of bid, c_{bid}^{avg} , for purchasing electricity from the reserve market to P2H for every level of P2H capacity as

$$c_{bid}^{avg}[l=2, l=3, \dots, L] = \sum_{l=2}^L \frac{C_{tot}^{bl} - C_{tot}^l}{\sum_i P_{P2H}^{el}(i)}. \quad (3.32)$$

C_{tot}^{bl} is the net production cost for the baseline, C_{tot}^l is the net production cost for each level of P2H capacity above the baseline, and P_{P2H}^{el} is electricity purchased via the reserve market. c_{bid}^{avg} is to be interpreted as the willingness-to-pay, or the average bid the utility can place for purchasing electricity from the reserve market before the baseline becomes cheaper.

3.8 Data sources

This section gives an overview of the data used in this thesis. In the appended Papers specific assumptions and numbers can be found.

3.8.1 Thermal data

For all Papers, the heat demands for the systems are simulated. Major reasons not to use measured data are the difficulties of getting actual data from the utilities, that aggregated regional heat demand data is not accessible, but also the fact that, to some extent, none of the studied systems exist today. In Paper I and II, the heat demand was simulated in the software VIP-Energy¹ with

¹ VIP Energy is validated according to ASHRAE 140-2007 and EN 1526-2007.

separate calculation of the distribution losses for the thermal distribution. This heat demand data was previously used in [121] and [122]. For Papers III-V, the DHS heat load was generated from outdoor temperature data and DHS annual heat production, according to a method described in detail in [123]. Outdoor temperatures for each location were retrieved from the Swedish meteorological and hydrological institute, SMHI [124]. In Paper IV, however, temperature measured by the local DH utility at the site of Hudiksvall was used.

The thermal capacities of the production units are, for all Papers except Paper III, dimensioned according to thermal loads and local climate of the specific study. Data on power production capacities in CHP plants is retrieved from the Swedish balance authority, Svenska Kraftnät [42], and the thermal capacity is based on data from the Swedish Environmental Protecting Agency [125].

3.8.2 Electrical data

Electricity production from BAPV in Paper I and II is simulated using a model based on the Hay and Davies model for irradiance on a tilted plane; the model is described in [98] and applied in [126]. Wind and solar power production on national level are in all Papers based on data retrieved from the Swedish balance authority, Svenska Kraftnät [127]. In Paper III and IV, the national power transmission capacity data for different electricity price regions for 2018 are obtained from Svenska Kraftnät [42].

The household electricity consumption in Paper I and II is simulated on minute resolution and then averaged to hourly resolution using the Widén Markov-chain model [128]. Data for national and electricity price regional electricity consumption are consumption data retrieved from NordPool [129].

3.8.3 Economic data

The discount rate used in Paper II is obtained from the Swedish Energy Market Inspectorate [130]. Investment cost for a DH distribution network is based on actual costs from Göteborg Energy AB in Sweden during their expansion of DH to sparsely built areas [44] and the cost for the end-user substation is retrieved from [64]. Investment costs for the CHP unit, large-scale heat pumps, TES, and EES as well as the operation and maintenance costs associated with these are obtained from literature [64], [131] - [134]. The purchase cost of electricity in Paper II is rudimentarily treated as a fixed cost based on the average price of the Nordic power system [33] and the selling price is assumed to be the same with a supplement charge of 15%.

In Paper V, the electricity price is based on hourly bidding profiles from NordPool [135], but adjusted to contain the volume of VRE used in the appended study. The cost of biomass, pellets, and natural gas is based on

forecasts made by the Danish Energy Agency [65]. Data for the depository fee for municipal solid waste used as fuel in CHP units is obtained from the industry organization Svenskt Avfall [80]. The cost for industrial waste heat as heat source is typically a contractual agreement and not based on market competition. In Paper V the cost for IWH use a figure from [123]. The cost for participating in the EU emission trade scheme (EU ETS) is based on personal correspondence with administrator at the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency [136]. The trading cost for green certificates to compensate for non-renewable production/consumption is based on estimates given by [137]. Natural gas taxation follows the CO₂-emission tax as well as the energy tax of Sweden [138]. Utilities using waste as fuel is subject to a waste incineration tax retrieved from the Swedish Government [139]. Finally heat pumps consuming electricity must pay electricity tax which is retrieved from the Swedish Tax Agency [140].

4 Results

In this chapter, the main results from the appended Papers are presented and compared. More detailed presentations of the results are found in the Papers. The comparison of the results follows the order of the research questions presented with the aim of the thesis (Section 1.1), and the investigated system levels of the individual studies as shown in Table 3.3. The following chapter is organized as follows; Section 4.1 summarizes results on power balancing services from the studied systems, Section 4.2 summarizes results for heat production, Section 4.3 presents performance of the heat storages, Section 4.4 presents results for biomass demand and GHG emissions. Finally, results for economic aspects from Paper II and V are provided in Section 4.5.

4.1 Power balancing

In this section, results for the supply of a VRE-induced power balancing demand (described in section 3.2) are presented. The results are presented for eight different heat production and supply systems, in five different contexts. Three systems (studied in Papers I and II) respond to one type of power balancing demand (P_{bal}), the five systems simulated in Papers III and IV respond to a somewhat differently defined P_{bal} , as explained in Section 3.2. The geographical location affects the share of wind/solar power in the VRE-mix as well as the transmission capacities to/from the area. This means that the magnitude of peaks and total amounts of surpluses and deficits vary between the different studies, see Table 4.1. This in turn, has an impact on the comparison of the results from the studies. It is, however, still reasonable to make an overall comparison of the potential for the systems to contribute with power balancing services. This comparison points out the general impact of the differences between systems configurations, i.e., production unit capacities, TES capacity and type, as well as amount of local VRE production and the shares of wind and solar in the VRE mix.

Table 4.1. Peak and annual balancing demand in the different Papers.

Paper	Year of data	Region	PRL		NRL	
			Annual	Peak	Annual	Peak
			GWh_{el}	MW_{el}	GWh_{el}	MW_{el}
I & II	2016	Local	0.4	0.2	0.1	0.2
			TWh_{el}	GW_{el}	TWh_{el}	GW_{el}
III	2018	SE3	36.2	14.6	0.9	0.8
IV	2020	SE1	2.8	1.6	2.1	2.8
		SE2	2.3	2.7	3.0	7.2
		SE3	32.5	13.6	0.3	4.6
		SE4	8.5	3.9	1.3	4.8

4.1.1 Electricity production and consumption

Figure 4.1 shows the share of P_{bal} supplied by the systems. The results are presented in four different “clusters”:

- *PRL, peak* – the peak electricity demand,
- *PRL, annual* – the annual electricity demand,
- *NRL, peak* – the peak surplus electricity,
- *NRL, annual* – the annual surplus electricity.

Each of these four clusters include results from the eight studied systems in the appended Papers. The suffix of each Paper number refers to the studied system of the Paper as presented in Figure 3.5. The system’s ability to cover PRL and NRL, as shown in Figure 4.1, are presented, respectively, in the following sections.

Positive residual load

The first cluster in Figure 4.1 shows the share of PRL peak demand in P_{bal} covered by the systems. The II-B system covered the largest share of the peak PRL demands among the studied systems. Systems III-sc2 and II-C also covered a significantly higher share of their PRL peak demand compared to the other five systems. The three systems with the largest coverage of the peak PRL are also the systems with the highest nominal electric output in CHP (II-B and III-sc2) and/or in flow batteries (II-B and II-C) which is shown in Table 4.2. The lowest share of the peak PRL was covered by system IV-2. This system had a theoretical possibility to supply between 2.5% and 9.4% of the peak PRL in P_{bal} depending on electricity price area. In Figure 4.1 error bars indicated the variation in balancing performance depending on electricity price area. The values for IV-1 and IV-2 are average values representing all four price areas. The reason why the error bar indicates that no PRL peak is reduced for some electricity price area in IV-2 is for temporal reasons. This matter will be further explained in the end of this section (on negative residual load).

The simulated system in III-ref was operated according to the ‘Heat Strategy’ and represents a theoretical maximal production for this setup. In reality, there are several factors impairing the achieved electricity production such as staffing, continuous fuel access, malfunctions, but also planned production targets set by biddings on the day-ahead market. In the simulations, it is assumed that the production can reach theoretical maximum potential without constraints. This becomes apparent when comparing the difference in supplied power balancing demand between the systems III-ref and III-sc1. Despite the fact that the electricity strategy, used in III-sc1, is designated to supply the power balancing demand, the III-sc1-system supplies only a 3% larger share of the peak balancing demand compared to the III-ref-system. However, production data for 2018 shows that electricity production from CHP units in SE3 during peak hour was only 51% of the nominal capacity. The reason why the CHP units do not operate at full capacity during peak demand hours is not known to the author, but can possibly be assumed to be related to the simplifications mentioned above regarding the assumption that production reaches the theoretical maximum. In comparison with production data, the simulation results in III-sc1 indicate that operating the CHP units according to the electricity strategy doubles the electricity supply during peak demand hour.

The second cluster of bars in Figure 4.1 shows that the annual power balancing demand (PRL, annual) is supplied to the largest extent (>30%) by systems II-B, I-132/II-A, III-sc1, and III-sc2. The lowest share of supplied annual power balancing demand is seen for system II-C. The reason for the poor performance for system II-C is that this system does not include a CHP unit, only an EES with a high-power output capacity, but with a low storing capacity. For the I-132/II-A-system, priority is given to the TES to supply the thermal peak demand. This means that less CHP heat capacity is required. The consequence of this is, however, a reduced power generation capacity to supply the

Table 4.2. Nominal electric output (CHP, WtE, EES) and consumption (HP) relative to peak PRL/NRL for respective scenario.

Paper	System	CHP	WtE	EES	HP
I	I-132	0.21	–	–	1.00
II	II-A	0.21	–	–	1.00
	II-B	0.43	–	0.76	–
	II-C	–	–	0.41	0.47
III	III-ref	0.12	0.03	–	–
	III-sc1	0.12	0.03	–	1.00
	III-sc2	0.57	0.03	–	1.00
IV	IV-1, average	0.06	–	–	0.05
	(range)	(0.03 – 0.09)			(0.02 – 0.13)
	IV-2, average	0.06	–	–	0.07
	(range)	(0.03 – 0.09)			(0.02 – 0.19)

Figure 4.1. Shares of P_{bal} supplied by the power balancing services in all different simulated systems presented in Paper I - IV. *PRL, peak* is peak electricity demand; *PRL, annual* is annual electricity demand; *NRL, peak* is peak surplus electricity; and *NRL, annual* is annual surplus electricity.

peak power balancing demand (as previously described for the first cluster in Figure 4.1). For I-132/II-A, the ‘Electricity Strategy’ was applied and despite the low nominal power output, the system supplied 41% of the annual power balancing demand. In II-B, 64% of the annual balancing demand is supplied by the system. This means that an increase in nominal power output with 100% only gave a 49% increase in supplied annual electricity demand. This is due to the ‘Heat Strategy’ where co-generation only occurs when heat and power demand coincide. The II-B-system does not contain a TES, which means that the CHP unit is dimensioned to cover the thermal peak demand. A larger heat output capacity also means that the CHP power output is larger, in this case doubled compared to system I-132/II-A, which enables the possibility to supply the electricity balancing demand to a greater extent.

Figure 4.1 shows that the III-sc2-system reduced the peak power balancing demand to a significantly greater extent than the III-sc1-system. However, the annual power balancing demand supply was almost the same for both systems. The reason is that the nominal CHP power output capacity for the III-sc2-system is about four times higher for the III-sc1-system. In III-sc1, the lower CHP capacity means that heat needs to be produced more continuously over the year to cover the annual heat demand, this despite operating according to the electricity strategy. In III-sc2, on the other hand, the CHP capacity is high enough for operating CHP plants shorter time spans and still cover the annual heat demand by using TESs. This explains the similar supply of annual power

balancing demand combined with a significant difference in supplied peak balancing demand.

The annual PRL supplied by III-ref is 20%. However, production data reported by the Swedish Energy Market Inspectorate [141] for 2018 on electricity generation in CHP units within the DHSs in SE3 shows that reported production merely corresponds to 13% reduction of the PRL in the study. This indicates that the potential for power balancing service from CHP units in the DHSs is used significantly less than their technical potential in terms of delivered electricity. When comparing reported production data with the results from III-sc1, it can be seen that electrical production increased by 58% in III-sc1.

The difference in the averaged annually supplied power balancing demand is quite small between systems IV-1 and IV-2, even though the TES capacity is doubled for IV-2. For both scenarios, the error bars indicate the variation in power balancing performance with respect to the different electricity price areas. For SE2, the annual PRL is reduced by 15%, while for SE1 it is only reduced by 3% for both IV-1 and IV-2. The reason to this variation is the different amounts of systems in the respective region, as shown in Figure 3.5, but also, more importantly, the different magnitudes of PRL to supply, as shown in Table 4.1. In Table 4.2 it also is shown that the capacity in heat pumps is higher in IV-2 compared to IV-1. The opposite is true for CHP plants, i.e., in IV-2 they have a slightly lower nominal capacity compared to IV-1. However, this difference is so small that it does not show up in Table 4.2. Nevertheless, these capacity changes in heat pumps and CHP plants contribute to the fact that there is no significant increase in PRL reduction for IV-2 compared to IV-1 despite the doubled TES capacity. With increased capacity in the heat pumps for IV-2, more heat is produced and also stored, becoming a competing heat supply to the DH network, which has a dampening effect on the output of the CHP plants.

Negative residual load

The third and the fourth clusters of bars in Figure 4.1 shows the supply of negative power balancing demand, NRL. For five of the studied systems, i.e., I-132/II-A, II-B, II-C, III-sc1, and III-sc2, all NRL is consumed. For II-B and II-C, the NRL is stored in an EES. For the I-132/II-A, III-sc1, and III-sc2, the NRL is used in heat pumps for heat production. The capacity of the heat pumps in these three systems is defined by the size of the NRL. System III-ref contains no heat pumps and no NRL is therefore reduced.

In Paper IV, the results vary between the four electricity price areas, as indicated by the error bars. For the peak NRL, the average reduction is 4% and 9.5% in scenarios IV-1 and IV-2, respectively. In SE2, peak NRL is reduced by about 3% for both systems, while in SE3, peak NRL is reduced by 12.5% and 15.5% for the same systems. For SE1 and SE4, however, peak NRL was not reduced at all. The fact that no peak reduction occurs in SE1 and SE4

is temporal. For example, in SE4, peak NRL occur in mid-June when the low heat demand is fully supplied by the already fully charged TES in both systems IV-1 and IV-2. Even though some heat is discharged from the TES, the amount of heat discharged is not enough to allow charging of the TES with heat from heat pumps (the TES is at this point filled to 99.75% which is considered full in the algorithm). Hence, the heat pumps are not activated since there is no possibility to use the produced heat. This is also the case for SE1. There are two aspects that are relevant here. (1) the magnitude of the NRL peak vary significantly between the regions, with the smallest value for SE1 and the largest for SE2, as shown in Table 4.1, (2) the capacities in heat pumps vary with, again, the smallest capacities in SE1 and the largest in SE3 (Table 4.2). Regarding the reduction of annual NRL, in the fourth cluster in Figure 4.1, differences in capacities and loads is important. SE3 has the smallest amount of annual NRL and SE1 has the smallest peak NRL values (Table 4.1). On average, the annual NRL is reduced by 16% and 18.5% for systems IV-1 and IV-2, respectively. The error bars indicate a significant spread in reduction between the regions. SE3 reduced the largest share, 38.5% and 47% for the two systems, this is due to the relation between heat pump capacities and magnitude of NRL, as previously described. The smallest reduction of NRL occurs in SE1, which again, relates to the small capacities in heat pumps simulated for this region.

4.2 Heat production

This section presents and compares heat production results from the simulations in the appended Papers. Initially, general findings are presented, followed by more specific explanations for each study.

Figures 4.2 and 4.3 are central for this section and will be referred to repeatedly. In Figure 4.2, the shares of heat produced from different heat production technologies are shown. Figure 4.3 shows how the heat supplied to DH distribution networks is allocated between the different technologies in each study. The production strategies and simulated technologies for the different studied systems are explained in Section 3.5.

The actual values used for Figure 4.2 are greater than the actual values used for Figure 4.3, for all but three systems (II-B, II-C, and III-ref, where none include TES). This is because Figure 4.2 includes TES losses and 4.3 only represents heat supplied to the DH distribution network. For system III-sc1 and III-sc2, the amount of produced heat in heat pumps is similar for the two systems (Figure 4.2) and the same goes for the amount of heat from heat pumps directly delivered to supply the DH load (Figure 4.3). This is expected since the amount of NRL is the same for these two systems. However, the share of heat delivered to DH distribution networks from TESs is significant (Figure 4.3). This indicates that for both systems the access to a storage

Figure 4.2. Allocation of heat production between different production technologies in the eight simulated systems, for IV-1 and IV-2 the four electricity price areas are shown also. The included technologies are heat pumps (HP) large-scale ground-source based or distributed air-to-air (in II-C only), combined heat and power (CHP), heat-only boilers (HoB), industrial waste heat recovery (IWH), and waste incineration (WtE).

Figure 4.3. Allocation of heat supplied to DH between different production technologies in the eight simulated systems. In system II-C no DH is present. TES means thermal energy storage and all other abbreviations are as described in Figure 4.2. For IV-1 and IV-2 the four electricity price areas of Sweden are shown as the allocation vary significantly.

enables heat production at times without a sufficient heat demand. Figure 4.2 also shows that for system III-sc2, the CHP production is significantly higher than for system III-sc1. This is because of the flexibility given by the storage

that can enable a high nominal power output capacity in III-sc2. For IV-1 and IV-2, the results significantly differ between the electricity price areas, which is shown by the stacked bars in both Figures 4.2 and 4.3. Figure 4.2 shows that a major difference between the different electricity price areas is the amount of heat produced in heat pumps, where SE3 has the lowest amount of heat from heat pumps. This is a direct effect of the available amount of NRL in each respective area. Figure 4.3 shows that the excessive use of heat pumps in SE1, SE2, and SE4 also lead to an extensive use of the TESs in comparison to SE3, which shows a significantly lower usage of the TESs. It can also be seen in Figure 4.2, when comparing IV-2 to IV-1, that the share of heat produced in heat pumps increase with access to larger TESs. Figure 4.3 further shows that the amount of heat produced in heat pumps to directly supply the heat demand, does not change significantly with increased size of TES. Just as for III-sc1 and III-sc2, this means that more NRL has been consumed in heat pumps at times where the heat demand is low and the produced heat is stored. This is also seen for system I-132/II-A, where 24% of the heat is delivered to the DH distribution network from the TES. This indicates a flexibility that is non-existing in systems without a TES, i.e., II-B, II-C, and III-ref.

For the systems presented in Paper III, the base-load supply to the DH load from IWH and WtE is similar for all three systems (see Figure 4.3). With a TES in III-sc1 and III-sc2, the total heat production is increased due to losses from the storage. This explains what looks like a relative decrease of heat produced in the base-load units in Figure 4.2 for these two systems, since the TESs losses are included, as explained previously. When comparing III-sc1 with III-ref, Figure 4.2 shows that the heat produced in the heat pumps primarily replace heat produced in CHP, but to some extent also heat produced in HoBs. When comparing system III-sc2 with III-sc1, Figure 4.2 furthermore shows that the production in CHP units is increased significantly, which is an effect of the system set-up as described in Section 3.5. In Figure 4.3, the same comparison shows that the TESs is used much more in III-sc2 (supply 28% of the heat demand), which imply an increased flexibility in this system compared to both III-sc1 and III-ref.

For the IV-1 and IV-2 systems, Figure 4.2 shows that the heat pumps account for between 5% and 47% of the total heat production in IV-1, depending on electricity price area. For system IV-2, with a doubled sized TES compared to IV-1, the heat pump share of total heat production is between 6% and 50%. For SE3 the heat pump capacity is changed from 13% of peak NRL in system IV-1 to 19% in IV-2, as indicated in Table 4.2. This partly explains the increased production from heat pumps in SE3. For all other electricity price areas, however, the heat pump capacity did not change between system IV-1 and IV-2. This means that the larger size of TES in itself enabled more production in the heat pumps since more NRL could be consumed and stored if the heat demand was too low. Figure 4.3 shows that TES supplied heat to DH between 9% and 52% of the time for system IV-1 and IV-2.

4.3 Heat storage

In the following section, results regarding the use and performance of TESs are presented and compared. Five out of the eight previously presented systems include TESs, hence these five systems are discussed here. The three systems studied in Paper V (V-HoB, V-WtE, and V-BioCHP) also use TESs and results for these will thus be presented here as well. The configurations of the different TESs simulated are presented in Section 3.5. From Paper V results are included for the scenario with 40 MW_{el} capacity in heat pumps. This is because in this scenario all stored heat was used, and the results are thus comparable with the other studied systems.

The results from the studies are presented and compared for four different parameters; storage capacity (4.3.1), thermal losses (4.3.2), degree of utilization (4.3.3), and efficiency (4.3.4). All four sections will refer to Figure 4.4 which shows above given parameters for the simulated systems. Figure 4.5 shows the hourly energy content in the TESs for a full year.

4.3.1 Storage capacity

Figure 4.4 a) shows the TESs storing capacity, P_{TES}^{cap} , relative to the annual heat demands, P_{HD}^{ann} , for the eight systems. The smallest system, I-132/II-A, has amongst the largest TES capacity relative to the annual heat demand (see also fourth column, Table 4.3). This is partly because the nominal thermal output of the CHP unit only is $0.5P_{HD}^{max}$ (162 kW_{th}), but mainly due to a seasonal application of the TES. This measure indicates large TES capacities is required for quite small power balancing capacity. Similarly, the III-sc1-system had a total nominal thermal output in the CHP units of only $0.38P_{HD}^{max}$ (3,618 MW_{th}), hence also requiring relatively large capacity of TES per annual heat demand. Comparing the I-132/II-A and III-sc1 systems with the other systems studied, a significantly lower capacity of TES is required in relation to the nominal thermal output of the respective CHP units, $P_{CHP}^{nom,th}$ (see column five, Table 4.3). Systems III-sc2, IV-1, and IV-2 have a thermal output in the CHP units closer to P_{HD}^{max} or above (see Table 3.5). This means that these systems have higher capacities in their CHP units enabling an operational strategy that supply higher levels of PRL demand compared to systems with smaller capacities in the CHP units. With lower CHP capacities the production is required to be more continuous in order to fully cover the heat demand. With high capacity in the CHP units follows also a larger amount of surplus heat that is stored, and longer time periods when the CHP units are shut down during which the TES, and/or heat pumps, supply the heat demand. Hence, the retention time in the TES is shortened and thereby also the required storage capacity per nominal thermal output in the CHP unit.

Table 4.3. TES volumes, thermal capacities (P_{TES}^{cap}) for the TESs, capacities relative annual thermal demands (P_{HD}^{ann}) and installed nominal thermal outputs of CHP and heat pumps, HP, as well as surface-area-to-volume ratio (SA:V) for the systems.

	Volume	P_{TES}^{cap}	$\frac{P_{TES}^{cap}}{P_{HD}^{ann}}$	$\frac{P_{TES}^{cap}}{P_{CHP}^{nom,th}}$	$\frac{P_{TES}^{cap}}{P_{HP}^{nom,th}}$	SA:V
	[m^3]	[GWh_{th}]	$\left[\frac{GWh}{MW_{HP}^{th}} \right]$	$\left[\frac{GWh}{MW_{CHP}^{th}} \right]$	[%]	
I-132/II-A	3,250	0.18	16.0	1.11	0.33	0.37
III-sc1	74.8×10^6	4 345.7	17.7	1.20	0.18	363.68
III-sc2	72.8×10^6	4 225.7	17.2	0.25	0.18	353.63
IV-1 average	90,000	4.21	1.0	0.09	0.08	0.18
(range)				0.08 – 0.09	0.07 – 0.11	
IV-2 average	180,000	8.42	2.0	0.18	0.14	0.18
(range)				0.21 – 0.17	0.14	
V-HoB	1.68×10^6	95.0	6.7	NA ¹	0.68	0.05
V-WtE	2.50×10^6	140.9	9.9	NA ¹	1.01	0.04
V-BioCHP	1.60×10^6	90.4	6.4	NA ¹	0.65	0.05

¹In Paper V the CHP units are not operated to provide power balance

In Paper V, the TESs is used to only store heat from heat pumps. Hence, it is reasonable to make a comparison for the TESs capacity relative the nominal thermal output in the heat pumps, $P_{HP}^{nom,th}$ instead of relative the CHP units as for the previous systems. Column six in Table 4.3 shows that V-WtE has the highest required TES capacity per nominal thermal output from the heat pumps compared to V-HoB and V-BioCHP, respectively. For system V-WtE, base-load supply from IWH and WtE (see Table 3.5) limits the possibility to use the TES on short-term, and instead requires longer storage times. In Figure 4.4 a), the TESs capacity relative the annual heat demand for the systems simulated in Paper V, is shown. It can be seen that these values are lower than for systems I-132/II-A, III-sc1 and III-sc2, but higher than for systems IV-1 and IV-2. This is mainly a result of the operational strategy applied in this study where only heat from heat pumps is stored in TES as described in Section 3.5.

The sizes of the TESs have been derived differently in the studies. For I-132/II-A, III-sc1, and III-sc2, the size was iteratively derived to enable consumption of all NRL and maximize the power balancing production in CHP units. For the two systems IV-1 and IV-2, the TES size is fixed and the storage size in IV-2 is two times the size in IV-1 (see Table 4.3). For systems V-WtE, V-HoB, and V-BioCHP, the storage size is iteratively derived to enable operation of P2H capacities on the power reserve capacity market. Depending on if the TES can be designed from optimization or if it is based on existing infrastructure, the operational flexibility of the system will vary. Furthermore, the operational priorities will impair the flexibility, i.e., depending on if the priority is to replace costly fossil-based peak load units for seasonal peak loads or to maximize the power production in CHP units. Or as in Paper V, to

maximize the use of P2H capacities as negative power balance. These different priorities imply different types of storage operation for seasonal or short-term time-horizon. Furthermore, whether stored heat is allowed to compete with other heat production units or only used as complementary resource, affects the required storage capacity.

4.3.2 Thermal losses

In Figure 4.4 b), the relative TES losses for the studied systems are shown. The TES in system III-sc1 have the highest relative losses (33%), while the lowest relative losses is for system V-BioCHP (0.6%). Differences in TES losses are explained by: the storage operation, physical properties of the storage, and the surface area-to-volume ratio (SA:V). For storages with high SA:V ratio, i.e., small volume relative the surface area, the operational strategy becomes crucial for the minimisation of losses. For all but the systems studied in Paper V, the average time that heat remains in the storage, i.e., the length of the storage cycles, thus has the greatest impact on the size of the storage losses. For systems I-132/II-A and III-sc1, the operation of the TESs is typically long-term, i.e., seasonal, which implies that the storage is only charged and discharged a few times per year. Long storage periods in general cause heat losses above 20% (see also Figure 4.5). For systems IV-1 and IV-2, the TESs are operated on shorter term, with storage cycles of weeks up to months. Short storage times yield annual losses of in general less than 10%. For III-sc2 the TES is operated with storing times between seasonal and monthly, thus ending up with relative losses in the mid-range $10\% < P_{loss}^h < 20\%$.

In Figure 3.3 the different physical forms of the simulated storages are shown. The TESs simulated in I-132/II-A, III-sc1, and III-sc2 (a) and b) in Figure 3.3) all have the top of the storage levelled with the ground surface. This means that there will be significantly higher losses through the top of the storage for these storages when compared to the TESs simulated in Papers IV and V (c) and d) in Figure 3.3), with the top of the storage >20 m below ground surface. This contributes to explain the significant difference in relative losses between the first three presented systems storages and the last five. For the storages simulated in system I-132/II-A and the two systems in Paper III, the losses up through the top of the storage represents a larger share of the storage losses compared to the losses through the other surfaces of the storage relative the surface areas. For I-132/II-A the losses through the top represent about 22% of the total losses through an area representing about 17% of the total surface area of the storage. Furthermore, the SA:V ratio is also contributing to the differences. With a large volume, there will be less surface area per unit volume through which heat can dissipate and this enables a more efficient TES. This, of course, strongly correlates with the actual geometric shape of the TES. As Table 4.3 show, the SA:V ratio correlates positively with the losses shown in Figure 4.4 b), i.e., high SA:V ratio yields high losses. The

reason to why the losses is so low for the systems studied in Paper V is that these TESs have optimal relation between height and radius to minimize the SA:V ratio, a geometric form that promotes a low SA:V ratio, and finally a position of the TES >25 m below ground surface.

4.3.3 Degree of utilization

Figure 4.4 c) shows the TESs degree of utilization, η_U , as described in Section 3.4.3, for the eight systems. A seasonal operational strategy of the TES, with a few cycles per year, yields a low η_U and a short-term TES yields a high η_U . A relatively small TES compared to DH demand coincides with high η_U . This is reasonable since small TES relative the annual heat demand is less suitable for long term storage. The heat is more efficiently used in short term perspective since the losses will be less.

Figure 4.4. Key performance values for the simulated TESs in the appended Papers. In a) the TES capacity relative the heat load is shown. In b) the thermal losses are shown and in c) and d) the degree of utilization and energy efficiency is shown respectively. The error bars for IV-1 and IV-2 indicates the spread between the regions simulated in that study.

The SA:V ratio for IV-1 and IV-2 (Table 4.3) are the same which could lead to the assumption that these two systems should have similar relative losses, but as Figure 4.4 b) show they do not. This is explained by the higher η_U for IV-1 compared to IV-2. A higher η_U means that more heat is cycled through the storage, which reduce losses in relation to the stored heat. The systems simulated in Paper IV with high η_U have the smallest storages capacities.

Figure 4.5 shows the normalized energy content over one year in TESs simulated for all systems. Figure 4.5 a) shows the TES for system I-132/II-A, Figure 4.5 b) shows the corresponding for systems III-sc1 and III-sc2. In 4.5 c) and d) is the energy content in TESs for all four electricity price areas in the two systems IV-1 and IV-2 shown. Finally, in Figure 4.5 e) is the TES for the three systems simulated in Paper V shown. The most pronounced short-term storage operation is represented by IV-1 and IV-2 as can be seen in Figure 4.5 c) & d). The III-sc2-system, shown in Figure 4.5 b), with a storage operation mixed between seasonal and short-term have a η_U of 2.6, which is slightly more than what is to be expected from a seasonal storage, i.e., only cycled 1-2 times over the year. This indicates that the storage has been used to a higher degree than just to supply seasonal peak heat demand, i.e., more flexibly operated. In Figure 4.5 b), the more flexible usage of TES in III-sc2 can be compared with the more typically seasonal operation of the TES in III-sc1 with a η_U of 1.06. When comparing III-sc2 with III-sc1 it can be seen that the storage in III-sc2 has a more irregular charge/discharge-pattern with more frequent charging/discharging. A similar charge/discharge-pattern can also be seen in Figure 4.5 e) for the TESs simulated in Paper V with V-BioCHP having the highest η_U of 3. This mix of seasonal and irregular pattern indicates a high flexibility in the operation of the TESs that distinguish these larger TESs from the highly pronounced short-term TESs in systems IV-1 and IV-2.

4.3.4 Energy efficiency

The energy efficiencies, η_E , of the eight systems are shown in Figure 4.4 d). The energy efficiency is given in Section 3.4.3 and indicates how efficiently the TES have stored the heat. For seasonal TESs, the η_E can be as low as 50% [142]. In relation to this, the results presented in this thesis are indicating fairly high performing storages. The lowest η_E is seen for the III-sc1-system (highest losses, lowest η_U) and the highest η_E is seen for the V-WtE and V-BioCHP-systems from Paper V. These systems have an η_E above 95%. The reason to why V-HoB have a lower η_E compared to the other two systems in Paper V can be seen in Figure 4.5. e). The black line for V-HoB indicate that the storage heat is not fully used during the year and also that there is a slight tendency for accumulation of heat, i.e., more heat in the TES at the end of the year than

Figure 4.5. Energy content in normalized values for all simulated TESs. Figure a) shows system I-132/II-A, and Figure b) shows TESs simulated in Paper III. Graphs c) and d) shows the TESs in systems IV-1 and IV-2, respectively. Finally, in e) the TESs simulated in Paper V are shown.

in the beginning. This, in turn, relates to the operational strategy of the TESs in the systems studied in Paper V. Regardless of this, however, the fact that not all heat is used lead to increased losses which reduces the η_E .

In Figure 4.6, the relation between relative losses, P_{loss}^h , and the inverse of SA:V, i.e., the volume-to-surface-area ratio, is shown. This means that opposite to the SA:V-ratio, a high V:SA-ratio instead indicates low losses. The size of the circles illustrates the degree of utilization, η_U , for all eight systems. The distribution of the circles shows how high V:SA give low P_{loss}^h and similarly low V:SA gives high P_{loss}^h . The two system with the highest losses is also the two most pronounced seasonally operated storages, I-132/II-A and III-sc1. The two systems with the highest η_U IV-1 and IV-2 are also the two systems with the most pronounced short-term TES operation. The high η_U for these

Figure 4.6. Relations between the relative losses in storage and the volume-to-surface-area ratio (the inverse of surface-area-to-volume ratio SA:V). The size of the circles represents the degree of utilization, η_U , of the storage.

two TESs reduces the relative losses and thus somewhat counterweight these storages low value of V:SA that otherwise would imply high losses. The III-sc2-system, however, with a storage operation in between seasonal and short-term, is situated somewhat in the middle of these two groupings, but with a tendency of seasonal operated storages regarding the quite low η_U and relative high losses compared to IV-1 and IV-2. With increasing V:SA follows a large storage capacity and hence also a reduced possibility for high η_U , illustrated in the Figure with reduced areas of the circles. With smaller storage size, i.e., smaller V:SA ratio, increases the possibility for high η_U . This can be seen with the increasing areas of the circles the closer to origo they are. The TESs with seasonal operational strategies, i.e., III-sc1, III-sc2, and I-132/II-A, are similarly showing a decreasing η_U the further away from origo in the diagram they are which is in line with the expected η_U of seasonally operated TESs.

4.4 Green-house gas emissions and fuel demand

This section presents results for the GHG-emission and fuel demand calculations for the eight studied systems. The systems in Paper V is not included since these systems are not operated according to the ‘Electricity strategy’ (described in Section 3.5). First, some general remarks are given, and after that more detailed results for each system are presented. The emissions accounted for are biomass use in CHP units and HoBs. Electricity produced by wind and solar are considered carbon neutral and do not cause emissions. No

life cycle assessment has been performed. Furthermore, the emissions from national base-load power production is constant for all simulation and not considered, as the analysis is focused on GHG from the DHSs power balancing supply.

System II-B is the reference system for all the systems in Paper I and II. In Paper III, system III-ref is the reference system, and in Paper IV, a system operated according to the ‘Heat Strategy’, without TES and heat pumps, and averaged for the four electricity price areas is the reference system (note that this reference system from Paper IV is not explicitly presented in this summary of the results). All reference cases should be considered ‘business as usual’-cases.

Figure 4.7 shows the shares of fuel use and indirectly also GHG-emissions allocated to electricity and heat production, respectively. The single-building and electricity-based heat supply for system II-C renders a significantly larger electricity demand compared to the other systems. This electricity demand is partly supplied by a condensing power plant fired with biomass. This, together with the lack of a DHS in the system explains the full allocation of fuel and emissions to electricity production.

For all other studied systems, except II-C, the shares of used fuels and GHG-emissions are similar. However, there are small, but notable differences between the systems operated according to the ‘Heat Strategy’, i.e., the reference systems, and the systems operated according to the ‘Electricity Strategy’. The difference is that systems operated with the ‘Electricity Strategy’ have a slightly larger share of fuel use and GHG-emissions from electricity production. This is because when CHP is operated according to the ‘Electricity Strategy’ the amount of produced electricity is higher compared to when operated according to the ‘Heat Strategy’. In the latter case, heat is occasionally produced without co-generation of electricity. For systems IV-1 and IV-2, the

Figure 4.7. Allocation of fuel use and GHG-emissions between electricity and heat production in the biomass fired CHP units for each simulated system.

allocation for the averaged reference system for all four electricity price regions is indicated with the dashed black line (23%).

In Figure 4.8, four different metrics for GHG-emissions are shown. In diagram a), GHG-emissions per produced unit of energy (i.e., both heat and electricity) are shown. In diagram b), the differences in fuel demand, as well as GHG-emissions, between the reference systems and the power balancing systems are shown. In diagram c), the GHG-emissions when allocated to electricity production are shown. Finally, in diagram d) emissions when allocated to heat production are shown.

The GHG-emissions per produced unit of energy in system II-C is significantly higher compared to the other systems (Figure 4.8 a). This is explained by the low efficiency of the condensing power plant. The difference in GHG-emissions is small for the other systems. In Paper III, GHG-emissions are calculated only for the biomass fired CHP and HoB units, i.e., the base load production from waste incineration and IWH is not included. The emissions for III-sc1 is slightly higher than for III-sc2. The difference between GHG-emissions between the systems from Paper I and II, and the systems in Paper III and IV, is mainly caused by different levels of energy conversion efficiencies of the boilers and generators in the simulations. The systems in Paper IV have the highest efficiency, they are assumed to be equipped with flue gas condensers, while the systems in Paper III have the lowest efficiencies as they represent an aggregate of CHP units in the entire electricity price area SE3.

Figure 4.8. GHG-emissions for the eight simulated systems. Diagram a) shows the specific GHG-emissions per unit useful energy (i.e., both heat and electricity). b) shows changed fuel use and GHG-emissions when compared to respectively reference system. In diagrams c) and d), the specific GHG-emissions when allocated to electricity or heat production respectively are shown.

The impacts on fuel demand and GHG-emissions from operating the systems according to the ‘Electricity Strategy’ are shown in Figure 4.8 b). In three of the systems (I-132/II-A, IV-1, and IV-2), is the heat production from the heat pumps sufficient to cover losses in the storage and to reduce heat production from biomass, thus reducing the fuel use compared to if operating the systems according to the ‘Heat strategy’. On the other hand, for system II-C there is a significant increase in fuel use in comparison to the reference system II-B, this since the electricity demand in II-C is supplied by a condensing power plant. In Paper III, fuel use for the balancing systems is higher than for the reference system because the amount of NRL is insufficient for heat produced in heat pumps to replace heat from biomass. However, as indicated by the error bars for III-sc1 and III-sc2, the fuel use is strongly dependent on the shares of PV and wind power in the VRE generation mix. High shares of PV promote heat pumps that replace fuels used in CHP units, but this is at the cost of reduced power balancing potential. The error bars for systems IV-1 and IV-2 represents the variations between the four electricity price areas. For SE3, fuel use is increased with 5% and 2%, and for SE1 decreased with 37% and 41% respectively for the different storage sizes compared to the averaged reference system.

When considering GHG-emissions relative the electricity production (Figure 4.8 c), the ‘Heat Strategy’-reference systems have higher emissions compared to the ‘Electricity Strategy’ systems. This confirms, as seen in Figure 4.7, that more GHG emissions are allocated to electricity production for the ‘Electricity Strategy’-systems as a result of the larger amount of electricity produced compared to for the ‘Heat Strategy’ systems. The averaged reference system for Paper IV is indicated with a dashed line in Figure 4.8 c) and d). The system with lowest emissions per produced unit of electricity is II-C with the condensing power plant. When considering GHG-emissions relative to produced heat (Figure 4.8 d), the magnitude of emissions in the results is reversed compared to Figure 4.8 c). That is, low emissions for the reference systems and high emissions for systems simulated with the ‘Electricity Strategy’. This is expected since heat is the main product in the reference systems and thus more heat is produced.

4.5 Economic aspects

In the following section, results for economic-viability are presented for three of the storage-based systems. In the end of the section, a summary of the results from Paper V is presented for the economic potential of DHSs to offer P2H capacities on the electricity reserve capacity market.

Figure 4.9 shows the economic viability results for the three storage-based systems A, B, and C (the same notation as in previous sections). An asterisk (*) means that the costs for the DHS distribution infrastructure in systems A

and B are excluded from the investment costs, i.e., assuming an existing distribution network. Systems B and C, which contain flow batteries are evaluated for two different cost scenarios for the flow batteries; one near-term, with a 20-year life time expectancy; and one optimistic scenario with a reduced cost and a life time expectancy of 30 years based on expected developments according to [134]. This optimistic scenario is indicated with the plus-sign (+).

Figure 4.9 a) presents the net present value, NPV, for the systems. In diagram b), the internal rate of return, IRR, is shown, diagram c) shows the profitability index, PI, and in d) the present value ratio, PVR, is shown. The system with the lowest NPV is II-B, i.e., the ‘Business as usual’, Figure 4.9 a). This is because this system is assumed to invest in a high capacity CHP unit, investment costly flow batteries, as well as a DH distribution network. The NPV is higher if the investment cost for the distribution network for DH is excluded (II-B*). Nonetheless, the substantially negative NPV still indicates that the system is economically unviable, which is explained by the remaining required high investment cost in high capacity CHP and flow batteries.

Figure 4.9. Economic results from Paper II. The Figure shows the net present value in a), the internal rate of return in b), the profitability index with the threshold >1 marked with a dashed line in c), and the present value ratio in d). * means the system was applied to an existing DH distribution infrastructure. + means an optimistic cost scenario for the flow batteries with 30-year life-time expectancy.

However, for system II-A, exclusion of the investment costs for the DH distribution network the crucial difference for economic feasibility.

The IRR (Figure 4.9 b) shows return on investment for both II-A and II-A*. Also, the system II-B*+, with the optimistic price scenario for EES, shows an IRR of zero. If EES in this system is used for other services, e.g., smart-charging or automatic frequency control, this might increase IRR since the initial capital cost could be partly or fully covered. All the other systems have negative IRR, meaning that the investment will not be able to cover the initial capital costs for the following 30-years. System II-C+, shows a significantly lower IRR compared to II-C, which is somewhat counter intuitive, since II-C+ is an optimistic scenario with reduced costs and long life-time expectancy for the EES. For II-C a reinvestment in EES is assumed after 20 years, and at the end of the assessed 30-year span, the residual value in the EES is deducted from the costs, i.e., assumed to be sold. This makes the IRR appear more economically viable for II-C compared to II-C+. This is not seen for the II-B-systems, because of the small positive cash flow, i.e., income, in II-C (only sold electricity). In the II-B-systems, income also comes from sold heat. This makes the impact of the reinvested EES much more apparent in the II-C-systems.

The PI indicates expected return per invested monetary unit and is shown in Figure 4.9 c). The highest PI (1.48) is seen for the II-A*-system, and implies that this power balancing system, when implemented in an existing DHS, returns 148% of the investments made. If, however, the investment costs for the distribution infrastructure is included, i.e., system II-A, the PI is 0.86. This indicates negative return and non-profitability for the system. For the fully electrified system, II-C, the PI is negative. This is because the revenue for this system is merely from electricity bought from and later supplied back to the power grid, i.e., small marginal for profit.

In Figure 4.9 d) is the PVR-values for the systems shown. For systems II-B and II-B*, the equal PVR-values show that the high investment costs for flow batteries are so high that the excluded investment costs for the DH distribution network in II-B* are not noticeable, making the systems equally economically inefficient in terms of capitalisation of the investment. Also, since no TES is included in system II-B, a larger and therefore more expensive CHP unit is required to supply the thermal peak demand. For II-B*+, with an existing DH distribution network and with an optimistic cost perspective for the EES, a capitalisation efficiency slightly lower than for the II-A system and economic infeasibility, is shown. As for the case of the IRR, this might be alleviated if other services for the EES are included in the business model, i.e., smart-charging or automatic frequency control.

In Table 4.4, an overall ranking is presented for the economic feasibility of the studied systems. According to the presented economic metrics here, system II-A*, i.e., a system with CHP, heat pumps and TES in an existing DHS distribution network, is the only economically feasible system. However, if a

TES is not possible to implement, II-B or II-C must be considered, i.e., ‘business-as-usual’ or a fully electrified system without DH.

Table 4.4. The systems ranked according to the different economic metrics used in the evaluation study, as well as a combined rank.

Ranking aspect	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
According to NPV	A*	A	B*+	B+, C+		B*	C	B
According to IRR	A*	A	B*+	B+	B, B*		C	C+
According to PI	A*	A	B*+	B+	B, B*, C+			C
According to PVR	A*	A	B*+	B+	B, B*, C+			C
Combined assessment	II-A*	II-A	II-B*+	II-B+	II-B*	II-C+	II-B	II-C

In Figure 4.10, cost balances and maximum average bidding costs for the systems studied in Paper V are shown. The amount of P2H-capacity active on the electricity reserve capacity market is shown on the x-axis. The y-axis shows cost, either net cost for production, or maximum average price per MW_{el} for bids on the reserve capacity market. The results show that all three systems can reduce the net-cost (solid lines) when bids for P2H-capacity on the reserve market is placed. This assumes that the average bidding price is the same or lower than the dashed lines in Figure 4.10. The dashed lines show the maximum average bidding price that is reasonable for the utilities, i.e. “willingness-to-pay”. The baseline, i.e., the reference case, indicates the level where no P2H capacity is traded on the reserve capacity market. For V-BioCHP, the “willingness-to-pay” is continuously increased with an increased P2H-capacity (dashed line). The reason for this is that the heat produced in P2H mainly

Figure 4.10. Net production costs (solid lines) for three different DHSs with P2H-capacities on the electricity reserve capacity market. The dashed lines show the maximum average cost per MW_{el} for P2H.

replace cost-intensive heat produced from fossil and pellets-based HoB, and heat pumps. For V-HoB and V-WtE, the “willingness-to-pay” is reduced with increased P2H-capacity. In the most extreme case of 60 MW_{el} P2H-capacity, this reduction is mainly caused by heat being produced and accumulated in TESs, i.e., a cost. The reason to why the “willingness-to-pay” is decreasing for V-HoB is that the relative impact of the electricity tax increase with the P2H-capacity. For V-WtE, there is a shift from expensive fossil fuels in HoB and biomass in the CHP unit, to P2H. This results in that the income from municipal solid waste (MSW) management is similar to the additional cost of electricity tax for increasing consumption of electricity in P2H. Hence, the willingness-to-pay for V-WtE appears fairly constant until the highest capacity of P2H, where the surplus heat is a cost due to accumulation of heat in the TES. It should, however, be pointed out that any price per MW_{el} below the bidding costs as shown in Figure 4.10 (dashed lines), is always economically beneficial for the DH utility. The investment cost for TES is not included in these results as the study only considers operational costs.

In Paper II, the prices for buying and selling electricity price are represented by an average system price. In Paper V, an hourly based electricity price is modelled, as described in Section 3.8.3, giving a more accurate representation of the earnings from sold electricity as well as costs for purchasing electricity (to heat pumps in V-BioCHP). Regardless of this discrepancy, it is possible to discuss and compare the outcome of the two studies. Given the results from Paper II, the economic potential for P2H on the reserve capacity market, shown in Paper V, further promotes a Smart Energy concept from a economic perspective when compared to a “business-as-usual”-case, or a fully electrified scenario. The operational strategy of the TESs as well as handling of competing heat production is of significant importance to further enhance economic feasibility of these power balancing sector-coupling systems.

5 Discussion and future work

In the following chapter, the findings presented are discussed in relation to the aims of the thesis. The results are also analysed from a systems perspective. The chapter ends with a reflection on future research targets.

Previous studies within the field are mainly focusing on the potential for P2H to manage VRE production surpluses. This is, however, merely a minor part of the overall aim of this thesis. In [143], the potential for accommodating large shares of VRE in Germany by using P2H as a flexible load is investigated. A similar study was performed for Sweden and is presented in [144]. Both of these studies indicate that there is a significant technical potential for flexible P2H production, which is also in line with the findings presented here. However, neither of these two studies investigate the impact of the variable nature of VRE and how this affects the potential for P2H in the context of smart energy systems. An interesting finding in this thesis is that the respective shares of wind and solar in the VRE production mix, as well as temporal distribution and annual share of PRL and NRL, have significant impact on the P2H potential to manage VRE surpluses. This also influences the optimal capacity and operation of TESs, and how to dimension CHP units. With a solar-dominated VRE production mix, a seasonal TES operation is necessary to accommodate the produced heat (as shown in Paper I). With a wind-dominated VRE production mix, however, the capacity needed and the operation of a TES rely on the temporal distribution of the VRE production. For example, the results in Paper III show that seasonal storing is preferably combined with low nominal capacity in CHP, when the latter is used for power balancing production. Furthermore, during low heat demand hours (typically in summer), CHP co-produces surplus heat when producing electricity for power balancing, and the heat from the TES is later used to supply peak heat demand. If the nominal capacity of the CHP units is higher, the operational scheme is rather “intra-seasonal”, i.e., with shorter retention times in the TES. This was also shown in Paper IV where heat production is frequently shifted between CHP and heat pumps, and the storage is therefore cycled more frequently.

In [145], the use of a TES was shown to introduce an increased flexibility to the heat production as it decouples heat production from the heat demand. This is also clearly in line with the findings in this thesis, especially in Paper I and IV, where it is shown that a CHP can be controlled by an electricity balancing demand instead of the local heat demand. A TES also increases the

potential to use heat produced in P2H as shown in [97]. However, in this thesis, the importance of competition for the local heat load among different heat supply technologies within a DHS is identified. Thus, an increased possibility to produce heat from P2H to manage VRE surpluses, comes with an inevitable competition for the heat demand with the other heat producing units, for example CHP. In a system where P2H production is primarily intended to be used as a power balancing service, i.e., to consume excess electricity, and a CHP is operated to cover power deficits, competition for the heat load will occur. If electric boilers are used, this competition will be less due to their lower heat production efficiency compared to heat pumps. Electric boilers simply consume more surplus electricity to produce a certain amount of heat compared to heat pumps. However, the lower efficiency of electric boilers means that there will be a higher exergy destruction, when high-quality electrical energy is irreversibly converted to low-quality thermal energy.

The properties of the above mentioned P2H technologies imply several things; (1) electric boilers can consume more surplus VRE than heat pumps for the same level of heat demand, (2) heat pumps produce more heat than electric boilers using the same amount of surplus VRE, (3) with access to capacity in a TES, both electric boilers and heat pumps will be less limited by the current heat demand level, (4) with access to TES, heat pumps have a larger potential to replace fossil fuelled peak load units, and/or reduce the need for biomass fuelled heat production. Hence, if the competing heat production units are fossil fuelled heat-only boilers, introduction of P2H from VRE can be argued to decarbonize the heating sector (e.g. as discussed by [146]) and in this case the competition is not an issue. On the other hand, if the competing heat supply unit is a CHP unit performing power balancing production, industrial waste heat, or heat from waste incineration plants, competition is a potential issue. This is particularly shown by the results in Paper V, where P2H units are operated according to the ‘Electricity Strategy’, while all other heat production is operated according to the ‘Heat Strategy’ to supply the local heat demand. The mix of these two operational strategies lead to a significant need of large TES capacity. This is because heat production occurs simultaneously in both P2H and the other heat producing units, which in turn is caused by the fact that there was no coordination between the units to avoid overproduction of heat. To the best of the author’s knowledge the issue of competition for heat demand has not been discussed frequently in the scientific community, but should be investigated further.

In [147], a similar Smart Energy-concept, as the ones studied in this thesis, is investigated, but without access to a large-scale TES. They conclude that the P2H unit’s potential is limited by the CHP unit’s operational constraints. This limitation could be attributed to the absence of a TES, which in Hast [148] is included along with P2H, HoB, and CHP units. Hast concludes that adding a TES could be cost effective if the share of VRE is large. However, they do not mention competition between CHP and P2H as an issue. This

relates likely to the scope of their study which is cost optimized production of heat, and not primarily power balancing. Hence, competition between technologies is a non-issue as long as the heat demand is fully supplied at the lowest possible cost. In [145], a matter is raised in terms of a “parasitic power consumption” when heat pumps use CHP generated power. This concerns neither competition for heat load nor usage of the TES. In all these three studies the heat production is the main purpose and thus any power balancing production is considered a by-product. In the studies presented in this thesis the power balancing production is the main product which, in contradiction to previous mentioned studies, makes the local heat demand a limiting factor for power production. This responds to the second sub-aim of this thesis. The heat load is a clear limitation for the power balancing production in CHP units for systems with PV dominated VRE production mixes, and seasonal TESs. This is because such a combination motivates low capacities in CHP units, as shown in appended Paper I. With wind dominated VRE production, the heat load is less constraining, which is especially true when combined with high capacities in CHP units. The latter, of course, comes with an additional investment cost for the CHP. In Paper III, it is shown that a high CHP capacity yields a high supply of balancing power, but reduces operation hours (from 5,800 h for the reference case down to 2,300 h for III-sc2). In Paper IV the relation between the shares of PRL and NRL in the P_{bal} is further analysed. These shares are affected both by the VRE production mix, but also the electricity demand. The results from Paper IV shows that regardless of the PRL/NRL-ratio an improved production flexibility is achieved in the studied systems. However, with a PRL/NRL-ratio closer to one, the added flexibility shows higher potential to promote power balancing production compared to with a large PRL/NRL-ratio. For SE3, the PRL/NRL-ratio is >100 and the net-load variability is reduced by a factor ten less than for the other regions with a PRL/NRL-ratio significantly closer to one (<10). Furthermore, the temporal distribution of P_{bal} is of relevance. In SE3, in particular, there is a significant seasonal pattern in P_{bal} which implies that long-term TESs might improve the flexibility more than the short-term TESs simulated in Paper IV. This is in line with the findings in Paper III, where the TES is of long-term capacity, but used as a short-term flexibility load. Also, this seasonal pattern seen for SE3 is in line with the finding in Paper I since a PV dominated VRE production mix, as in Paper I, yields a similar seasonal pattern. Hence, a long-term TES can be motivated also for cases where the electricity demand affects P_{bal} to result in strong seasonal differences.

With this knowledge, the response to the first sub-aim of the thesis, which considers the possibility to improve the production flexibility for power balancing, is that the flexibility can be improved, but to a varying extent. First, adding a TES does improve the flexibility, which is in line with findings in several other studies ([97], [145], [149], [150]), but it also adds another source for supply of heat to the DH that occasionally becomes a competing heat that

can hamper CHP or P2H production. Second, as described above, the characteristics of the VRE production mix and electricity demand significantly affect the potential for the achieved flexibility to promote power balancing services to the power system.

The use of biomass responds to the third aim of this thesis, i.e., the reduction of biomass demand and consequently also reduction of GHG-emissions. In Lamaison [151] they conclude that with scarce access to biomass, a seasonal TES is necessary to reach high shares of renewable energy in the energy system. As shown in Paper I, III, and IV (for SE3) it is not a necessity that implementation of TESs and an operation according to the electricity strategy automatically reduce the demand for biomass. In fact, the fuel use may be higher for such a system, compared to a conventional DHS. This relates to the first sub-aim of the thesis in the following way: Power balancing production does not necessarily coincide in time and/or match the level of the heat demand and the surplus heat must then be stored. For systems with TES, additional heat needs to be produced to cover the storage heat losses, and this, in turn, could induce increased fuel use. The findings in Paper III and IV further confirm this by indicating that even if the TES is not seasonal, the fuel use may still be higher compared to a reference case with no TES, depending on the share of P2H-produced heat. In the second scenario in Paper III, the nominal output capacity of the CHP units was quadrupled compared to the capacity in scenario 1, while the VRE production mix was unchanged. However, the operation of the TES was changed from “inter-seasonal” to “intra-seasonal” between the two scenarios. This is explained by the increased capacity of the CHP units and not the amount of NRL in the electricity balancing demand. Furthermore, the amount of NRL in both scenarios was too small to enable heat pumps to produce a sufficient amount of heat in order to decarbonize the DHS. The analysis of the VRE mix in Paper III shows that the fuel demand decreases with higher shares of PV in the VRE mix compared to the original case in the study. In Paper IV, the impact of the VRE mix on fuel use is further assessed by adding the aspect of the annual amount of PRL vs NRL as well as the temporal distribution of these, as previously mentioned. It is interesting that for SE4, with less than half the share of VRE relative the electricity demand compared to SE2, a similar significant reduction in fuel use is shown. However, in SE3 the fuel use should be reduced, but is instead increased when compared to the reference case. The reason is a low total amount of VRE relative the electricity demand which means that P2H replace biomass-fuelled heat to less extent. This emphasizes the impact of a suitable balance between PRL and NRL, in order for P2H to reduce fuel use in a power balancing system. Hence, the impact of applying an electricity strategy on fuel use, requires thorough and specific analyses for each individual case.

The fourth aim of this thesis focuses on economic strengths and weaknesses for power balancing systems such as the ones examined in this thesis. One economic strength is the dual income from CHP heat and electricity for DHS

operators. Another strength could be that P2H production reduces fuel costs. This, however, depends on the fuels used within the system. The study presented in [7] shows that implementing P2H in large scale reduces the risk for negative electricity prices when VRE production is high, because the demand for surplus electricity is increased. Furthermore, the study presented in [152] shows that the NordPool electricity spot-price level would not necessarily control P2H production to reduce surplus VRE power. Hence, controlling heat pumps via the primary reserve market to more directly contribute to the overall system efficiency might be necessary, as investigated in Paper V. In Paper II, the investment and operating costs for three different heating and storage-based solutions were analysed and compared. The results show that if all infrastructure is needed, none of the studied systems reached a PI greater than one. If heavy investments are problematic, gradual expansion may be preferable. In existing DHSs, the investments are potentially less problematic, since the large investments in CHP units and the distribution network are in many cases already made. In systems without existing DHS, step-by-step investments are probably relevant to consider. Investments in DH are, however, infrastructural commitments that include both production units and a distribution system. This means that the possibility of gradually expanding such a system is limited. Therefore, investments in systems with EESs instead of a DHS appear to be more manageable, as they are module-based. Thus, without an external actor (public or private) willing to take the financial risk, EES-based systems are probably most likely to be invested in. This is because EES-based systems are more suitable for distributed expansion. To avoid sub-optimal system solutions that might induce undesirable power imbalances, it might be required with governmental policies that enables actors to strive for system solutions that optimize the overall system efficiency in the long run.

In the introduction, power supply capacity shortages to and from several Swedish and European urban areas, was mentioned. The issue of urban area capacity shortage is important since it elucidates the importance of local and controllable power generation capacity within urban areas, such as CHP power generation capacity. DHSs are local entities supplying a local heat demand, but are in many cases also connected to a national power market. The fact that they are local entities are especially relevant when it comes to the capacity shortage in to urban areas. There are currently ongoing tests of local power balancing markets within some selected urban areas in the EU project CoordiNet. The city of Uppsala is one [153], [154]. Here, local actors are given the opportunity to place bids for local production or consumption to alleviate capacity shortages. The findings presented in this thesis (Paper II) indicate that, depending on chosen system configuration, the issue of power capacity shortages in urban areas can be either worsened or partially mitigated. Another method to cope with capacity shortage that is often discussed is demand side management (DSM) that generally describes how energy consumption better can match the production [155]. The core of DSM is to actively

shift consumers' electric load to better match the power production by either reducing, during peak demand, or increasing, during low demand hours, the consumption [156]. Currently, well established methods exist for the tertiary reserve market of industrial DSM (e.g., aluminium electrolysis plants, electric arc furnaces). This kind of demand side measures are, however, associated with significant costs for the transmission system operator and are most suited for temporary load shifting [157]. Thus, in the long run, industry-DSM would be cumbersome in economic terms for the transmission system operator and problematic for industry when there is a need to maintain production. Demand side management of household appliances is another strategy that often is discussed. This potential is, however, shown to be limited. In [158] the need of back-up power in a future renewable scenario for Europe by implementing DSM for household appliances is shown to be approximately 4-7%. The findings in this thesis indicate, in comparison to this, a reduction of the annual PRL with 43% (Paper I), 31% (Paper III), and 9% (Paper IV). It can thus be concluded that both DSM and power balancing smart energy systems may be required to alleviate net load variability in a future energy system with large shares of VRE.

The coupling of multiple different energy carriers, such as heat, electricity, gas, and/or hydrogen, from parallel systems into a coordinated operation scheme defines a multi-carrier energy system. If the production units in such a system, in combination with energy storage, are coordinated to achieve, for example, power grid stability, it is often referred to as a virtual power plant (VPP) in the literature. There are two main types of VPPs: commercial and technical [159]. Commercial VPPs are not constrained by geographical location, but can include actors and assets from many different locations. Technical VPPs consist of resources and users from the same geographic location. A VPP can, however, be of both types at the same time. Typically, VPPs focus on distributed VRE generation and how to perform load shifting via electrical storage, demand-side management, or thermal production via P2H, i.e., operated in a multi-carrier energy system. From this point of view, the system configuration studied in Paper I, i.e., with access to distributed PV generation, combined with a central heat pump and large-scale TES, can be considered as a VPP as in [160]. However, a DHS is typically not considered a VPP even though may include production assets that produce both electricity and heat and even have access to TES. It is then more relevant to acknowledge the sector-coupling aspect of heating-sector production units to provide electricity power balancing services. Such power balancing system can then be considered a smart energy system [161], gaining from synergies through sector-coupling, where a VPP may be one type of all systems included.

There are effects of a large-scale TESs that have not been covered in detail in this thesis, but are of significant relevance. Experiences from the DHS in Hudiksvall indicate that the possibility to operate the CHP unit within an optimal efficiency range improves the fuel economy and reduces emissions of

NO_x, SO_x, and other particles. The TES in Hudiksvall also contributes with redundancy to the production system and thus increases the production resilience. This, in turn, is experienced to reduce stress among the staff during troubleshooting, and also reduces the need of working in shifts. Finally, an aspect not covered at all in the appended studies is the need for rotating mass or inertia in a power system to maintain a stable network frequency. Rotating mass enhances the power systems resilience on power quality. A large share of VRE generation means less rotating mass in nuclear and coal power plants. CHP units, however, can be used as synchronous condensers and thus add rotating mass to the system which strengthen the power quality and short-circuit capacity [162], [163].

Given the current concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere, methods for removing CO₂ from the atmosphere are becoming increasingly relevant. Bioenergy carbon capture and storage uses biomass for sequestration of CO₂ and thus reach negative net emission [164]. This is promising for biomass fired heat and electricity generation, particularly if combined with P2H to decarbonize the heat production. There is currently a carbon capture test facility for capturing biogenic CO₂ from a CHP plant in Stockholm, Sweden [165].

Future work

Smart energy systems, as defined in this thesis, requires a heat demand. This limits the possibility to implement these systems to warm climates. In an international perspective, however, the principle of these smart energy systems could also be applied to district cooling systems. District cooling is a growing market and holds other correlations between NHL and cooling demand than those that can be seen between NHL and heating demand in colder regions and hence these require to be investigated. A possibility is to include sorption chillers connected to a TES that can use stored heat for production of cooling. In this way, the possible utilization of a TES could be increased. In DH cooling systems both sorption chillers and heat pumps can be included since heat pumps simultaneously produce heat and cold while consuming electricity (see Figure 3.1).

Another interesting area for continued work is to use sophisticated forecasting to optimize production and use of TESs in DHSs. This means developing strategies for system operation to handle the stochasticity of VRE power generation, while using a TES as a buffer. Operation strategies can be optimized to minimize emissions, costs, or heat losses, while maximizing power balancing production.

Conversion of low-grade heat to electricity is generally inefficient. There are technologies available for this, for example organic Rankine cycle-based CHP (as suggested as CHP unit in Paper I), Stirling engines, or thermoelectric generators [166]. These technologies are all associated with very low

efficiencies, below 15-20%. Nevertheless, if surplus heat is abundant, a low efficiency might not necessarily be a crucial obstacle. It could be interesting to explore the possibilities to use low-grade heat for power balancing production via some of these technologies.

In this thesis, the heat demand has been shown to be a limiting factor. Expansion of DHS is generally limited by the heat demand density. However, if thermochemical energy storages [167], with no storage losses, are charged with surplus heat and distributed to end users outside the DH network [168], such a solution could possibly reduce the limitation of local urban area heat demand levels. This would, however, imply development of new heat exchanging units at end users, new business models for the DH utilities, and new infrastructural distribution systems. A distributed DHS based on thermochemical energy storages could, however, be an interesting future research topic.

6 Conclusions

In this chapter the main conclusions from the appended Papers are summarized and presented in relation to the aims of the thesis

Flexibility in power balancing services

In line with current research, it is stated in this thesis that including CHP, heat pumps and TESs for the heat supply in a DHS increases the production flexibility and the system's redundancy. It is specifically pointed out here that these well-established technologies can be used in a novel way. The DH operator could use the flexibility provided by a TES to operate the heat and electricity production to primarily supply an electricity balancing demand. However, in order not to increase the fuel demand, heat pumps are required, and a significant amount of NRL is necessary. The results from Paper III and IV highlight the importance of the operation of the TES, the amount and temporal distribution of NRL from VRE generation, as well as the nominal power generation capacity of the CHP units. The following conclusion are drawn:

- PV dominated VRE production and/or low nominal capacity in CHP plants yield seasonal storage operations and high required capacity for P2H. This also means large amounts of operating hours as well as annual electricity produced in CHP, but limited potential for peak power demand reduction.
- Wind dominated VRE production and/or large nominal capacity in CHP plants yield short-term storage operations (intra-seasonal) with good capacity for peak power demand reduction and moderate to small required capacity for P2H.

Factors limiting the power-balancing services

Increased utilization of NRL for heat production in P2H-units increases the competition between different heat supplying units to supply the local heat demand. If P2H replaces fossil-based HoBs, GHG-emissions from the fuel use are reduced. In that case, the system is somewhat decarbonized and the matter of competing heat supply technologies is not an issue. If, however, P2H production reduces the possibility for a CHP unit to produce balancing power,

this competition is an issue to be considered in the production planning. In Paper I, power balancing production from CHP units is shown to be limited in systems with PV dominated VRE production mixes and seasonally operated TESs. For such systems, there is no necessity for high capacities in CHP units. This is because the TES can supply seasonal peak heat demands with P2H produced surplus heat. For wind power dominated VRE production mixes, however, the power balancing production is less limited. This is because wind power is less seasonally dependent in comparison with solar power. For these cases TESs can be operated more intra-seasonally and are thus not a competing technology to CHP units for seasonal peak heat demand supply. This enables the possibility to have higher capacities in CHP units, which further enables the intra-seasonal operations of the storage. However, higher capacities in CHP units of course come with additional investment costs. This was exemplified and showed in Paper III.

Effects on fuel demand from producing balancing power

As was shown in Paper I, III, and IV the fuel demand is not necessarily reduced by implementing a TES and adapting a production strategy to supply an electricity balancing demand. In fact, the fuel use may be higher for such a system, compared to systems without a TES and with a conventional heat production strategy. So, in response to the first aim of the thesis, for systems that store heat seasonally, the heat losses from TESs require additionally produced heat that might increase fuel use. However, if heat production is not fuel based, for example with heat pumps that use NRL to produce heat, fuel use can be reduced. Hence, to clarify whether an electricity strategy applied for a system with CHP, heat pumps, a TES and DH, actually will reduce the fuel demand, thorough and specific analysis are required for each individual system, and for different production conditions.

Economic possibilities for implementing a power balancing smart energy system

Based on the findings presented in Paper II it is concluded that, since power balancing systems with DH, CHP, heat pumps and TESs are large-scale system solutions with high investment costs, the economic risk is high and the rate of return of the investments is low. At least under the current economic conditions. Hence, it may not be possible to rely on market-based solutions for an expansion of this type of infrastructure projects. To reduce the risk of investment policy instruments and incentives would be required. On the other hand, for systems with existing DH distribution networks and CHP units there may be an opportunity to re-evaluate the operational strategies and investigate how to include heat pumps and TESs to be able to handle an electricity mix

with large shares of VRE. It can furthermore be concluded from the results of Paper V, that P2H capacities on the reserve capacity market could generate significant cost reduction for the DH operators. This, however, depends strongly on the DH utilities' other production units, HoB, CHP, WtE, etc., but also incentives and/or tax reductions from the government.

In conclusion the results of this thesis show that DH operators can provide significant amounts of power balancing with a smart energy system configuration, where the power balancing services include both production and consumption of electricity, enabled by the access to a TES acting as a flexible heat load. Furthermore, it should be emphasized that the share of PV in the VRE production mix is essential in order to achieve a reduced demand of biomass for heat production, which, in turn, underlines the need for a large-scale TES with the possibility for long-term operation.

7 Sammanfattning på Svenska

Sedan industrialiseringens början har användningen av fossil energi bidragit till en global växthuseffekt med drastiskt ökade CO₂-nivåer i atmosfären. Ett sätt att uppnå minskade utsläpp är att öka andelen elproduktion från förnybara energikällor såsom sol-, vind-, och vattenkraft samt biomassa. I Sverige kan inte kapaciteten hos vattenkraften ökas ytterligare och biomassa är en resurs med begränsningar. Elproduktion från sol- och vindkraft är väderberoende, vilket innebär att det inte är efterfrågan på el som avgör när elen produceras utan väderförhållandena. En storskalig utfasning av icke förnybar elproduktion (olja, kol, naturgas och kärnkraft), ersatt med ökad produktion från variabel förnybar el (variable renewable electricity, VRE), medför ett ökat behov av reservkraftkapacitet för att täcka underskott i elförsörjningen från VRE. Under gynnsamma väderförhållanden finns det å andra sidan en risk för att produktionen av el från VRE överstiger efterfrågan. För att hantera utmaningen med överskottsel från VRE-produktion kan olika åtgärder vidtas, t.ex. bortkoppling av produktion, förstärkning av överföringskapaciteten i elnäten, utökad ellagringskapacitet, eller laststyrning med flexibla laster som kan matcha elöverskott respektive elbrist.

En annan utmaning för den framtida energiförsörjningen är urbaniseringen och det ökade behovet av överföringskapacitet in till städer som detta medför. I takt med att befolkningen i städerna ökar, transporter elektrifieras, och elintensiva industrier etableras ökas belastningen på överföringskapaciteten till städerna. Detta innebär att en ökad elproduktionskapacitet utanför städerna inte nödvändigtvis kommer att kunna tillgodose en ökad efterfrågan på el inom städerna. Flexibel elproduktionskapacitet i urbana områden kommer sannolikt vara en framtida utmaning. Det behövs kontrollerbar kraftförsörjning för att täcka produktionsbrister.

I tätbebyggelse med tillräckligt höga värmebehov finns ekonomiska förutsättningar för fjärrvärmesystem. I den här avhandlingen ligger fokus på fjärrvärmesystem med biomassabaserad produktion. I fjärrvärmesystem är det även relativt vanligt förekommande med kraftvärmeverk (KVV) som samproducerar värme och el, ett sätt att nå en hög total bränsleomvandlingseffektivitet. Kraftvärme är en kontrollerbar elproduktionskapacitet som typiskt anläggs i anslutning till tätbebyggda områden och kan därför potentiellt bidra till att minska utmaningen med bristande överföringskapacitet.

Elpannor och kompressorbaserade värmepumpar är andra väletablerade storskaliga tekniker för värmeproduktion. I dessa förbrukas el vid produktion av värme, ofta benämnt power-to-heat (P2H), vilket möjliggör användandet av dessa som en flexibel ellast. Fjärrvärmesystem med KVV och värmepumpar eller elpannor kan potentiellt drivas för att täcka underskott samt konsumera överskott av el från VRE-produktion. Värmelasten består huvudsakligen av värmebehov för uppvärmning av lokaler i byggnader, och detta behov varierar avsevärt mellan säsongerna. Effektbehovet på värmelasten kan därmed vara begränsande för produktionen från KVV och värmepumpar under delar av året. Med tillgång till storskaliga värmelager kan dock flexibiliteten i värmelasten ökas. I denna avhandling undersöks om ett fjärrvärmesystem med KVV, värmepumpar och värmelager kan användas för att bidra till ökad flexibilitet i kraftbalanseringen i ett framtida energisystem med en stor andel VRE. Ett sådant system, vars produktion planeras utifrån elbehovet, drivs då på ett för fjärrvärmesektorn okonventionellt sätt som liknar vad som i den vetenskapliga litteraturen kallas Smarta Energisystem. Smarta energisystem innebär att driften av olika energisektorer samordnas för att uppnå högre systemeffektivitet. Dessutom undersöks hur dessa tjänster påverkar bränslebehovet samt systemens ekonomiska förutsättningar.

I denna avhandling simuleras 12 olika fjärrvärmesystemtyper i ett framtida scenario med stor andel sol- och vindkraft i elproduktionen. Systemen består av KVV, värmepumpar och storskaliga värmelager placerad på olika systemnivåer (från lokal nivå, via aggregerad regional nivå, upp till nationell nivå) och med varierande kapaciteter samt andra produktionsenheter (se Figur 3.5). Genom att låta befintligt elbehov förses med el producerad från sol- och vindkraft motsvarande 10% respektive 60% av det totala elbehovet, definierades ett kraftbalanseringsbehov. Detta kraftbalanseringsbehov innehåller timmar med behov av mer elproduktion, men även timmar med överskott på el. De studerade systemen simuleras att följa detta kraftbalanseringsbehov i sin produktion. Det innebär att om kraftbalanseringsbehovet är positivt så finns det ett elbehov varvid KVV producerar el och värme. Är kraftbalanseringsbehovet negativt finns ett elöverskott och då konsumerar värmepumparna denna el genom värmeproduktion. Den producerade värmen från KVV och/eller värmepumpar levereras till fjärrvärmenätet eller lagras i värmelagret. Vid tillfällena då det varken finns ett elbehov eller elöverskott råder balans mellan produktion och konsumtion av el. I dessa fall förses eventuellt värmebehov med lagrad värme. Så sker även när då den producerade värmen från KVV och/eller värmepumpar understiger värmebehovet.

Resultaten visar att reducering av topplastbehoven och/eller elöverskottstoppar framförallt styrs av den installerade kapaciteten i KVV:en och/eller värmepumpar. Den över året varierande värmelasten blir begränsande för potentialen att reducera elöverskott via värmepumpar. Stora mängder elöverskott gör även att det produceras stora mängder värme i värmepumparna. Denna

värme riskerar att ytterligare begränsa potentialen för kraftbalansering vid senare tidpunkter.

Årlig elproduktion ökar med tillgång till värmelager och produktionen planerad utifrån kraftbalanseringsbehovet. Mängden årlig reducerad överskottsel beror dels på den installerade kapaciteten i värmepumparna, men även på tillgång till kapacitet i värmelager.

Det finns tydliga samband mellan hur lagret används, dess form och hur stora förlusterna blir. Ett lager med stor mantelarea relativt dess volym har sämre lagringsförmåga jämfört med ett lager med liten mantelarea relativt dess volym. I viss mån kan förlusterna som kommer av ett ofördelaktigt förhållande mellan mantelarea och volym kompenseras genom en ökad omsättning av den lagrade värmen. De största lagerförlusterna fås från lager med lång lagringstid (ex.v. säsongslagring) samt har en stor mantelarea relativt lagervolymen.

Ett annat resultat är sambandet mellan bränsleanvändning i KVV:en och mixen av sol- respektive vindkraft i kraftbalanseringsbehovet. En solkraftsdominerad elmix främjar produktion i värmepumpar och säsongslagring. Värmen producerad i värmepumparna ersätter bränslebaserad värmeproduktion vilket innebär minskat bränslebehov. Det innebär också en reducerad potential för kraftproduktion från KVV på grund av konkurrens om värmelasten.

En vindkraftsdominerad elmix, å andra sidan, motiverar mer kraftproduktion i KVV samt högre kapacitet, men även ökat bränslebehov. För denna elmix blir lageranvändningen mer korttidsbetonad.

Resultaten pekar på att det finns tydliga ekonomiska fördelar med samordnade intersektionella energisystem. Värme producerad i värmepumpar som drivs på billig överskottsel kan konkurrera ut dyra fossilbränslen som används till årliga topplastperioder, men den kan även ersätta dyrare förädlade biomassabränslen såsom pellets i värmepannor. Dock kan nätavgifter, anslutningsavgifter samt skattesatser komma att utgöra hinder för en effektiv etablering av P2H som kraftbalanseringstjänst. För fjärrvärmeoperatören finns även behov av nya affärsmodeller där fjärrvärmebolagen får ersättning för att utföra kraftbalanseringstjänster. Drifttimmarna för KVV:n blir signifikant mycket färre då deras produktion planeras utifrån kraftbalanseringsbehovet istället för värmebehovet vilket påverkar lönsamhet samt motivering till investering.

Sammanfattningsvis visar resultaten i denna avhandling att fjärrvärmesektorn kan leverera betydande mängder kraftbalansering om dessa producerar utifrån ett systemtänk i linje med Smarta Energisystem, där kraftbalanseringstjänsterna omfattar både produktion och konsumtion av el, möjliggjort genom tillgång till ett värmelager som agerar flexibel värmelast. Dessutom bör det betonas, att andelen solceller i mixen av VRE-produktion är avgörande för att uppnå en minskad efterfrågan på biomassa för värmeproduktion, vilket i sin tur understryker behovet av storskaliga värmelager med möjlighet till långsiktig lagring.

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Bibliography

- [1] The Keeling Curve [WWW Document], n.d. . The Keeling Curve. URL <https://sioweb.ucsd.edu/programs/keelingcurve> (accessed 9.14.20).
- [2] Paris Agreement - Status of Ratification | UNFCCC [WWW Document], n.d. URL <https://unfccc.int/process/the-paris-agreement/status-of-ratification> (accessed 9.14.20).
- [3] Hirth, L., Ziegenhagen, I., 2015. Balancing power and variable renewables: Three links. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 50, 1035–1051. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.04.180>
- [4] KOSTOV, P., 2019. CoordiNet [WWW Document]. Innovation and Networks Executive Agency - European Commission. URL <https://ec.europa.eu/inea/en/horizon-2020/projects/h2020-energy/grids-storage-energy-systems/coordinet> (accessed 8.23.20).
- [5] Press Release [WWW Document], n.d. URL <https://www1.nyc.gov/site/buildings/about/pr-sustainable-roof-requirements.page> (accessed 9.15.20).
- [6] Frederiksen, S., Werner, S.E., 2013. District heating and cooling, 1. ed. *Studentlitteratur*, Lund.
- [7] Kirkerud, J.G., Bolkesjø, T.F., Trømborg, E., 2017. Power-to-heat as a flexibility measure for integration of renewable energy. *Energy* 128, 776–784. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.03.153>
- [8] Guelpa, E., Verda, V., 2019. Thermal energy storage in district heating and cooling systems: A review. *Applied Energy* 252, 113474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113474>
- [9] Lund, H., Werner, S., Wiltshire, R., Svendsen, S., Thorsen, J.E., Hvelplund, F., Mathiesen, B.V., 2014. 4th Generation District Heating (4GDH). *Energy* 68, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2014.02.089>
- [10] Kumbartzky, N., Schacht, M., Schulz, K., Werners, B., 2017. Optimal operation of a CHP plant participating in the German electricity balancing and day-ahead spot market. *European Journal of Operational Research* 261, 390–404. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2017.02.006>
- [11] Ma, Z., Knotzer, A., Billanes, J.D., Jørgensen, B.N., 2020. A literature review of energy flexibility in district heating with a survey of the stakeholders' participation. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 123, 109750. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.109750>
- [12] Levihn, F., 2017. CHP and heat pumps to balance renewable power production: Lessons from the district heating network in Stockholm. *Energy* 137, 670–678. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.01.118>
- [13] Lund, H., Duic, N., Østergaard, P.A., Mathiesen, B.V., 2018. Future district heating systems and technologies: On the role of smart energy systems and 4th generation district heating. *Energy* 165, 614–619. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.09.115>
- [14] IPCC, 2021: Summary for Policymakers. In: *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment*

- Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S. L. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M. I. Gomis, M. Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J.B.R. Matthews, T. K. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu and B. Zhou (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press. In Press.
- [15] IEA – International Energy Agency [WWW Document], 2021. IEA. URL <https://www.iea.org> (accessed 10.13.21).
- [16] Swedish Energy Agency, 2021. Electricity production (net production) by type of power from 1970, TWh. PxWeb [WWW Document], n.d. URL https://pxexternal.energimyndigheten.se/pxweb/en/%c3%85rlig%20energibalans/%c3%85rlig%20energibalans_El-%20och%20fj%c3%a4rrv%c3%a4rmeproduktion/EN0202_25.px/table/chartViewAreaStacked/ (accessed 10.13.21).
- [17] Du, P., Baldick, R., Tuohy, A. (Eds.), 2017. Integration of Large-Scale Renewable Energy into Bulk Power Systems, Power Electronics and Power Systems. Springer International Publishing, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-55581-2>
- [18] Holttinen, H., 2005. Hourly wind power variations in the Nordic countries. *Wind Energ.* 8, 173–195. <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.144>
- [19] Kaspar, F., Borsche, M., Pfeifroth, U., Trentmann, J., Drücke, J., Becker, P., 2019. A climatological assessment of balancing effects and shortfall risks of photovoltaics and wind energy in Germany and Europe. *Adv. Sci. Res.* 16, 119–128. <https://doi.org/10.5194/asr-16-119-2019>
- [20] Lledó, Ll., Torralba, V., Soret, A., Ramon, J., Doblas-Reyes, F.J., 2019. Seasonal forecasts of wind power generation. *Renewable Energy* 143, 91–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2019.04.135>
- [21] Widén, J., 2011. Correlations Between Large-Scale Solar and Wind Power in a Future Scenario for Sweden. *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy* 2, 177–184. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSSTE.2010.2101620>
- [22] Svenska Kraftnät, 2020. Varför delades Sverige in i fyra elområden 2011? [WWW Document], n.d. URL <https://www.svk.se/utveckling-av-kraftsystemet/systemansvar--elmarknad/elomradesoversyn/fragor-och-svar-om-elomradesoversyn/varfor-delades-sverige-in-i-fyra-elomraden-2011/> (accessed 12.10.21).
- [23] Svenska Kraftnät, 2018. Både kort- och långsiktiga lösningar behövs för att möta kapacitetsbristen [WWW Document], n.d. URL <https://www.svk.se/press-och-nyheter/nyheter/allmanna-nyheter/2018/bade-kort--och-langsiktiga-losningar-behovs-for-att-mota-kapacitetsbristen/> (accessed 12.10.21).
- [24] Ding, F., Mather, B., 2017. On Distributed PV Hosting Capacity Estimation, Sensitivity Study, and Improvement. *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy* 8, 1010–1020. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSSTE.2016.2640239>
- [25] Energipolitikens inriktning Proposition 2017/18:228 - Riksdagen [WWW Document], n.d. URL https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/proposition/energipolitikens-inriktning_H503228/html (accessed 8.12.19).
- [26] Svenska Kraftnät, 2021. [WWW Document] <https://www.svk.se/om-kraftsystemet/kraftsystemdata/elstatistik/> (accessed 10.14.21)
- [27] Svenska Kraftnät, 2019. Nordic Grid Development Plan 2019. June 2019. Statnett, Fingrid, Energinet, Svenska Kraftnät. [WWW Document] <https://www.svk.se/press-och-nyheter/nyheter/allmanna-nyheter/2019/nordisk-natutvecklingsplan/> (accessed 10.13.21).

- [28] Swedish Energy Agency, 2016. *Fyra framtider – Energisystemet efter 2020. Explorativa scenarier*. April 2016. ET 2016:04 [WWW Document] <https://www.energimyndigheten.se/fyraframtider> (accessed 10.13.21)
- [29] Swedish Energy Agency, 2021. *Scenarier över Sveriges energisystem 2020, mars 2021*. ER 2021:6. ISSN 1403-1892, ISBN (pdf) 978-91-89184-93-0.
- [30] Levelized Cost of Energy and of Storage [WWW Document], n.d. . Lazard.com. URL <http://www.lazard.com/perspective/levelized-cost-of-energy-levelized-cost-of-storage-and-levelized-cost-of-hydrogen/> (accessed 10.14.21).
- [31] Obaid, Z.A., Cipcigan, L.M., Abraham, L., Muhssin, M.T., 2019. Frequency control of future power systems: reviewing and evaluating challenges and new control methods. *J. Mod. Power Syst. Clean Energy* 7, 9–25. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40565-018-0441-1>
- [32] Svenska Kraftnät, 2020. Information om stödtjänster [WWW Document], n.d. URL <https://www.svk.se/aktorsportalen/systemdrift-elmarknad/information-om-stodtjanster/> (accessed 12.10.21).
- [33] NordPool, 2021. See what Nord Pool can offer you. [WWW Document], n.d. URL <https://www.nordpoolgroup.com/> (accessed 12.13.21).
- [34] Lund, P.D., Lindgren, J., Mikkola, J., Salpakari, J., 2015. Review of energy system flexibility measures to enable high levels of variable renewable electricity. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 45, 785–807. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.01.057>
- [35] Wang, J., Zong, Y., You, S., Træholt, C., 2017. A review of Danish integrated multi-energy system flexibility options for high wind power penetration. *Clean Energy* 1, 23–35. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ce/zkx002>
- [36] Bundesnetzagentur, 27th Nov, 2019. Monitoring report 2019, n.d. 531.
- [37] Tonkoski, R., Lopes, L.A.C., 2011. Impact of active power curtailment on overvoltage prevention and energy production of PV inverters connected to low voltage residential feeders. *Renewable Energy* 36, 3566–3574. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2011.05.031>
- [38] Luo, X., Wang, J., Dooner, M., Clarke, J., 2015. Overview of current development in electrical energy storage technologies and the application potential in power system operation. *Applied Energy* 137, 511–536. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.09.081>
- [39] Buijs, P., Bekaert, D., Cole, S., Van Hertem, D., Belmans, R., 2011. Transmission investment problems in Europe: Going beyond standard solutions. *Energy Policy* 39, 1794–1801. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.01.012>
- [40] Werner, S., 2017. District heating and cooling in Sweden. *Energy* 126, 419–429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.03.052>
- [41] Beiron, J., Montañés, R.M., Normann, F., Johnsson, F., 2020. Combined heat and power operational modes for increased product flexibility in a waste incineration plant. *Energy* 202, 117696. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.117696>
- [42] Svenska Kraftnät, 2018. Power balance on the Swedish electricity market, report 2018 (in Swedish). *Kraftbalansen på den svenska elmarknaden, rapport 2018; 2018. 2018-06-28, diary number 2018/587*. URL <https://www.svk.se/siteassets/om-oss/rapporter/2018/kraftbalansen-pa-den-svenska-elmarknaden-rapport-2018.pdf>
- [43] Svensk författningssamling (SFS 2008:263). Sveriges Riksdag. [WWW Document] https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/_sfs-2008-263 (accessed 10.15.21)

- [44] Reidhav, C., Werner, S., 2008. Profitability of sparse district heating. *Applied Energy* 85, 867–877. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2008.01.006>
- [45] Pelda, J., Holler, S., Persson, U., 2021. District heating atlas - Analysis of the German district heating sector. *Energy* 233, 121018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.121018>
- [46] Werner, S., 2013. District Heating and Cooling, Chapter in Reference Module in Earth Systems and Environmental Sciences, Ed. Scott a. Elias et al., Elsevier, 2013. pp 841-848.
- [47] Frederiksen, S., Werner, S.E., 2013. District heating and cooling, 1. ed. Studentlitteratur, Lund.
- [48] Gadd, H., Werner, S., 2013. Daily heat load variations in Swedish district heating systems. *Applied Energy* 106, 47–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2013.01.030>
- [49] Werner, S., 2017. District heating and cooling in Sweden. *Energy* 126, 419–429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.03.052>
- [50] Brueckner, S., Miró, L., Cabeza, L.F., Pehnt, M., Laevemann, E., 2014. Methods to estimate the industrial waste heat potential of regions – A categorization and literature review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 38, 164–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.04.078>
- [51] Vallios, I., Tsoutsos, T., Papadakis, G., 2009. Design of biomass district heating systems. *Biomass and Bioenergy* 33, 659–678. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2008.10.009>
- [52] Moser, S., Puschnigg, S., Rodin, V., 2020. Designing the Heat Merit Order to determine the value of industrial waste heat for district heating systems. *Energy* 200, 117579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.117579>
- [53] Averbalk, H., Ingvarsson, P., Persson, U., Gong, M., Werner, S., 2017. Large heat pumps in Swedish district heating systems. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 79, 1275–1284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.135>
- [54] Sayegh, M.A., Danielewicz, J., Nannou, T., Miniewicz, M., Jadwiszczak, P., Piekarska, K., Jouhara, H., 2017. Trends of European research and development in district heating technologies. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 68, 1183–1192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.02.023>
- [55] Lund, H., Werner, S., Wiltshire, R., Svendsen, S., Thorsen, J.E., Hvelplund, F., Mathiesen, B.V., 2014. 4th Generation District Heating (4GDH). *Energy* 68, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2014.02.089>
- [56] Buffa, S., Cozzini, M., D’Antoni, M., Baratieri, M., Fedrizzi, R., 2019. 5th generation district heating and cooling systems: A review of existing cases in Europe. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 104, 504–522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.12.059>
- [57] Østergaard, P.A., Lund, H., Mathiesen, B.V., 2016. Smart energy systems and 4th generation district heating. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy Planning and Management* 1-2 Pages. <https://doi.org/10.5278/IJSEPM.2016.10.1>
- [58] Lund, H., Hvelplund, F., Vad Mathiesen, B., Aalborg Univ, Department of Development and Planning, 2011. Coherent energy and environmental system analysis. A strategic research project financed by The Danish Council for Strategic Research Programme Commission on Sustainable Energy and Environment.
- [59] Lund, H., Østergaard, P.A., Connolly, D., Mathiesen, B.V., 2017. Smart energy and smart energy systems. *Energy* 137, 556–565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.05.123>

- [60] Lund, H., 2014. Renewable Energy in District Heating and Cooling, A sector roadmap for REmap 112.
- [61] Mathiesen, B.V., Lund, H., Connolly, D., Wenzel, H., Østergaard, P.A., Möller, B., Nielsen, S., Ridjan, I., Karnøe, P., Sperling, K., Hvelplund, F.K., 2015. Smart Energy Systems for coherent 100% renewable energy and transport solutions. *Applied Energy* 145, 139–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.01.075>
- [62] Lund, H., Østergaard, P.A., Connolly, D., Ridjan, I., Mathiesen, B.V., Hvelplund, F., Thellufsen, J.Z., Sorknæs, P., 2016. Energy Storage and Smart Energy Systems. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy Planning and Management*, Vol 11 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.5278/ijsep.2016.11.2>
- [63] Sandberg, E., Kirkerud, J.G., Trømborg, E., Bolkesjø, T.F., 2019. Energy system impacts of grid tariff structures for flexible power-to-district heat. *Energy* 168, 772–781. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.11.035>
- [64] Gudmundsson, O., Thorsen, J.E., Zhang, L., 2013. Cost analysis of district heating compared to its competing technologies. Presented at the ENERGY AND SUSTAINABILITY 2013, Bucharest, Romania, pp. 3–13. <https://doi.org/10.2495/ESUS130091>
- [65] Energistyrelsen. Samfundsøkonomiske beregningsforudsætninger for energipriser og emissioner. 2017 apr. https://ens.dk/sites/ens.dk/files/Analyser/samfundsoekonomiske_beregningsforudsætninger_2017_ver_2.pdf.
- [66] Alvarez, H., 2006. *Energiteknik: D. 1, 3. opl.* ed. Studentlitteratur, Lund.
- [67] Strömberg, B., 2006. Fuel Handbook, Project number of Swedish version F4-324
- [68] IRENA (2017), Renewable Energy in District Heating and Cooling: A Sector Roadmap for REmap, International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi. www.irena.org/remap.
- [69] Gonzalez-Salazar, M.A., Kirsten, T., Prchlik, L., 2018. Review of the operational flexibility and emissions of gas- and coal-fired power plants in a future with growing renewables. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 82, 1497–1513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.278>
- [70] Hentschel, J., Babić, U., Spliethoff, H., 2016. A parametric approach for the valuation of power plant flexibility options. *Energy Reports* 2, 40–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2016.03.002>
- [71] Skytte, K., Olsen, O.J., 2016. Regulatory barriers for flexible coupling of the Nordic power and district heating markets, in: *European Energy Market (EEM), 2016 13th International Conference on The. IEEE*, pp. 1–5.
- [72] Kirkerud, J.G., Trømborg, E., Bolkesjø, T.F., 2016. Impacts of electricity grid tariffs on flexible use of electricity to heat generation. *Energy* 115, 1679–1687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2016.06.147>
- [73] Bergaentzlé, C., Jensen, I.G., Skytte, K., Olsen, O.J., 2019. Electricity grid tariffs as a tool for flexible energy systems: A Danish case study. *Energy Policy* 126, 12–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.11.021>
- [74] Johannsen, R.M., Arberg, E., Sorknæs, P., 2021. Incentivising flexible power-to-heat operation in district heating by redesigning electricity grid tariffs. *Smart Energy* 2, 100013. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segy.2021.100013>
- [75] Statistics Sweden, 2020. Electricity supply, district heating and supply of natural and gasworks gas 2019. EN11SM2001. ISSN 1654-3661 [WWW Document] <https://www.scb.se/en/finding-statistics/statistics-by-subject-area/energy/energy-supply-and-use/annual-energy-statistics-electricity-gas-and-district-heating/pong/publications/electricity-supply-district-heating-and-supply-of-natural-and-gasworks-gas-2019/> (accessed 10.19.21)

- [76] Göransson, L., Lehtveer, M., Nyholm, E., Taljegard, M., Walter, V., 2019. The Benefit of Collaboration in the North European Electricity System Transition—System and Sector Perspectives. *Energies* 12, 4648. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12244648>
- [77] Eriksson, O., Finnveden, G., 2017. Energy Recovery from Waste Incineration—The Importance of Technology Data and System Boundaries on CO2 Emissions. *Energies* 10, 539. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en10040539>
- [78] Danish Energy Agency. Flexibility in the power system - Danish and European experiences. Danish Energy Agency; 2015. October 2015. [WWW Document] https://ens.dk/sites/ens.dk/files/Globalcooperation/flexibility_in_the_power_system_v23-lri.pdf (accessed 10.20.21)
- [79] Agora Energiewende, 2017. Flexibility in thermal power plants - With a focus on existing coal-fired power plants (Study No. 115/04-S-2017/EN). Europäisches Zentrum für Wirtschaftsforschung und Strategieberatung, Berlin.
- [80] Swedish Waste Management 2019, 2020. Avfall Sverige (in Swedish). URL: <https://www.avfallsverige.se/in-english/> (accessed 20210426)
- [81] Le Dréau, J., Heiselberg, P., 2016. Energy flexibility of residential buildings using short term heat storage in the thermal mass. *Energy* 111, 991–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2016.05.076>
- [82] Bolander, D.-A., n.d. Capacity utilization for Power-to-Heat in Swedish district heating systems. ISSN: 1650-8300, UPTEC ES18 026. Master thesis (in Swedish).
- [83] Ivanova, P., Sauhats, A., Linkevics, O., 2019. District Heating Technologies: Is it Chance for CHP Plants in Variable and Competitive Operation Conditions? *IEEE Trans. on Ind. Applicat.* 55, 35–42. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIA.2018.2866475>
- [84] K. Skytte and O. J. Olsen, "Regulatory barriers for flexible coupling of the Nordic power and district heating markets," 2016 13th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM), 2016, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/EEM.2016.7521319.
- [85] Trømborg, E., Havskjold, M., Bolkesjø, T.F., Kirkerud, J.G., Tveten, Å.G., 2017. Flexible use of electricity in heat-only district heating plants. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy Planning and Management* 29-46 Pages. <https://doi.org/10.5278/IJSEPM.2017.12.4>
- [86] Ding, Y., Riffat, S.B., 2013. Thermochemical energy storage technologies for building applications: a state-of-the-art review. *Int. J. Low-Carbon Tech.* 8, 106–116. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ijlct/cts004>
- [87] Scapino, L., Zondag, H.A., Van Bael, J., Diriken, J., Rindt, C.C.M., 2017. Sorption heat storage for long-term low-temperature applications: A review on the advancements at material and prototype scale. *Applied Energy* 190, 920–948. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.12.148>
- [88] André, L., Abanades, S., 2020. Recent Advances in Thermochemical Energy Storage via Solid–Gas Reversible Reactions at High Temperature. *Energies* 13, 5859. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13225859>
- [89] Hale et al., 1971. Phase change materials handbook. NASA contractor report. NASA CR-61363
- [90] Sharma, A., Tyagi, V.V., Chen, C.R., Buddhi, D., 2009. Review on thermal energy storage with phase change materials and applications. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 13, 318–345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2007.10.005>

- [91] Fleischer, A.S., 2015. *Thermal Energy Storage Using Phase Change Materials*, SpringerBriefs in Applied Sciences and Technology. Springer International Publishing, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-20922-7>
- [92] Alva, G., Lin, Y., Fang, G., 2018. An overview of thermal energy storage systems. *Energy* 144, 341–378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.12.037>
- [93] Fisch, M.N., Guigas, M., Dalenbäck, J.O., 1998. A review of large-scale solar heating systems in Europe. *Solar energy* 63, 355–366.
- [94] Claesson J, Efring B, Eskilson P, Hellström G. *Markvärme. En handbok om termiska analyser. Del 1 Allmän del (T16:1985)*. Swedish Built Environment Research Council; 1985, ISBN 91-540-4461-8.
- [95] Lizana, J., Chacartegui, R., Barrios-Padura, A., Valverde, J.M., 2017. Advances in thermal energy storage materials and their applications towards zero energy buildings: A critical review. *Applied Energy* 203, 219–239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.06.008>
- [96] Eriksson, R., 2016. Heat storages in Swedish district heating systems. An analysis of the installed thermal energy storage capacity. Master thesis. Halmstad University; 2016. URN: urn:nbn:se:hh:diva-31143
- [97] Holmér, P., Ullmark, J., Göransson, L., Walter, V., Johnsson, F., 2020. Impacts of thermal energy storage on the management of variable demand and production in electricity and district heating systems: a Swedish case study. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy* 39, 446–464. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786451.2020.1716757>
- [98] Duffie, J.A., Beckman, W.A., 2013. *Solar engineering of thermal processes / John A. Duffie, William A. Beckman*, 4th ed. ed. John Wiley, Hoboken.
- [99] Dannemand Andersen, J., Bødker, L., Jensen, M.V., n.d. Large Thermal Energy Storage at Marstal District Heating. Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Soil Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering, Paris 2013, 3351-3354.
- [100] Hesaraki, A., Holmberg, S., Haghighat, F., 2015. Seasonal thermal energy storage with heat pumps and low temperatures in building projects—A comparative review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 43, 1199–1213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.12.002>
- [101] Allen, K., von Backström, T., Joubert, E., Gauché, P., 2016. Rock bed thermal storage: Concepts and costs. Presented at the SOLARPACES 2015: International Conference on Concentrating Solar Power and Chemical Energy Systems, Cape Town, South Africa, p. 050003. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4949101>
- [102] Dahash, A., Ochs, F., Janetti, M.B., Streicher, W., 2019. Advances in seasonal thermal energy storage for solar district heating applications: A critical review on large-scale hot-water tank and pit thermal energy storage systems. *Applied Energy* 239, 296–315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.01.189>
- [103] Pauschinger, t., Schmidt, T., Soerensen, P. A., Snijders, A., Djebbar, R., Thornton, J., 2018. Design Aspects for Large-Scale Aquifer and Pit Thermal Energy Storage for District Heating and Cooling. Task A – State-of-the Art Review. September, 2018. www.iea-dhc.org
- [104] Lund, H., Østergaard, P.A., Connolly, D., Ridjan, I., Mathiesen, B.V., Hvelplund, F., Thellufsen, J.Z., Sorknæs, P., 2016. Energy Storage and Smart Energy Systems. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy Planning and Management*, Vol 11 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.5278/ijsepm.2016.11.2>
- [105] Rulli MC, Bellomi D, Cazzoli A, De Carolis G, D'Odorico P. The water-land-food nexus of first-generation biofuels. *Sci Rep* 2016;6:22521. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep22521>.

- [106] IEA. Delivering Sustainable Bioenergy. Paris: IEA Technology Roadmaps, IEA; 2017. p. 51. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264287600-en>.
- [107] Gerssen-Gondelach SJ, Saygin D, Wicke B, Patel MK, Faaij APC. Competing uses of biomass: Assessment and comparison of the performance of bio-based heat, power, fuels and materials. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2014;40:964e98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.07.197>.
- [108] Heck, V., Gerten, D., Lucht, W., Popp, A., 2018. Biomass-based negative emissions difficult to reconcile with planetary boundaries. *Nature Clim Change* 8, 151–155. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-017-0064-y>
- [109] Zottl, A., Nordman, R., Miara, M., 2012. Seasonal performance factor and monitoring for heat pump systems in the building sector, SEPEMO-Build. Benchmarking method of a seasonal performance. D4.4 Benchmarking method of seasonal performance under consideration of boundary conditions. IEE/08/776/SI2.529222
- [110] Swedish Energy Agency, 2020. Air-to-air heat pumps 2009–2013. [WWW Document], n.d. Swedish Energy Agency. Available at <https://www.energimyndigheten.se/tester/tester-a-o/luftluftvarmepumpar-2009-2013/?showTable=1&showTable=1&showTable=1&showTable=1> (accessed 14 February 2020)
- [111] Sarbu, I., Sebarchievici, C.: ‘Ground-source heat pumps: theory and experimental research’ (Elsevier Science & Technology, London, 2015), ch. 2.4, p. 13. Available at ProQuest Ebook Central [12 August 2019]
- [112] Çengel, Y.A., Boles, M.A., 2011. Thermodynamics: an engineering approach, Seventh in SI units. ed. McGraw-Hill Education, New York, NY, (p. 578).
- [113] Schmidt T, Sørensen PA. Monitoring Results from Large Scale Heat storages for District Heating in Denmark. 14th International Conference on Energy Storage 25-28 April 2018. Adana TURKEY; 2018.
- [114] HEAT3 – Heat transfer in three dimensions – Buildingphysics.com, n.d. URL <https://buildingphysics.com/heat3-3/> (accessed 9.19.21).
- [115] Blomberg, T. 1996. Thesis. Heat conduction in two and three dimensions. Computer modelling of Building Physics applications. Department of Building Physics, Lund University. P.O. Box 118, S-221 00 Lund, Sweden. Report TVBH-1008. ISRN LUTVDG/TVBH--96/1008--SE/1-188. ISBN 91-88722-05-8.
- [116] Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, 2019. Calculation of greenhouse gas emissions [WWW Document], n.d. Naturvårdsverket. Available at <https://www.naturvardsverket.se/Stod-i-miljoarbetet/Vagledning/Luft-och-klimat/Berakna-dina-klimatutslapp/> (accessed 5 Nov 2021)
- [117] Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, 2019: ‘National inventory report’. Sweden 2019. Greenhouse Gas Emissions Inventories 1990–2017
- [118] 2.10.2 Direct Global Warming Potentials - AR4 WGI Chapter 2: Changes in Atmospheric Constituents and in Radiative Forcing [WWW Document], n.d. URL https://archive.ipcc.ch/publications_and_data/ar4/wg1/en/ch2s2-10-2.html (accessed 11.24.21).
- [119] Sherman, E.H., 2015. A manager’s guide to financial analysis: powerful tools for analyzing the numbers and making the best decisions for your business, Sixth. ed. American Management Association, New York, NY.
- [120] Macdonald, E.H., 2007. Evaluation, risk and feasibility, in: Handbook of Gold Exploration and Evaluation. Elsevier, pp. 553–599. <https://doi.org/10.1533/9781845692544.553>
- [121] Åberg, M., A. M. Nilsson, J. Munkhammar, R. Luthander, D. Lingfors, and J. Widén., 2016. ”Electricity Self-Sufficiency and Primary Energy Use in a

- Swedish Residential Community, after Building Renovation and Implementation of Photovoltaics, Small-Scale CHP, and Electric Vehicles.” In Proceedings of the 2016 ACEEE Summer Study on Energy Efficiency in Buildings, Pacific Grove, CA, USA, August 21-26 (2016) 11:1-13 [aceee.org/files/proceedings/2016/data/.../11_152.pdf](https://www.aceee.org/files/proceedings/2016/data/.../11_152.pdf)
- [122] Monie, S., Nilsson, M. A., Lingfors, D., Widén, J., Åberg, M., 2018. Thermal Energy Storages in Residential Areas – a potential to increase renewable power generation? In proceedings of the ACEEE Summer Study on Energy Efficiency in Buildings, Pacific Grove, CA, USA, 12 – 17 August 2018.
- [123] Åberg, M., Widén, J., 2013. Development, validation and application of a fixed district heating model structure that requires small amounts of input data. *Energy Conversion and Management* 75, 74–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2013.05.032>
- [124] Utforskaren - Öppna data | SMHI [WWW Document], n.d. URL <https://www.smhi.se/data/utforskaren-oppna-data/se-acmf-meteorologiska-observationer-lufttemperatur-timvarde> (accessed 10.28.21).
- [125] Swedish Environmental Protecting Agency, 2005. (In Swedish) Förbränningsanläggningar för energiproduktion inklusive rökgaskondensering (utom avfallsförbränning). Stockholm: Naturvårdsverket; March, 2005. <https://docplayer.se/4223986-Forbranningsanlaggningar-for-energi-produktion-inklusive-rokgaskondensering-utom-avfallsforbranning.html>
- [126] Lingfors, D. 2015. “Solar Variability Assessment and Grid Integration: Methodology Development and Case Studies.” Licentiate thesis. Uppsala University, 2015.
- [127] Svenska Kraftnät, 2021. Power statistics (In Swedish) [WWW Document], URL. 2021. https://www.svk.se/aktorsportalen/elmarknad/kraftsystemdata/elstatistik/?_t_id¼qWowEhUA1rBRRNtzXdqH-w¼¼&_t_uuid¼VA3RVYr9RKA0thIDr04L6Q&_t_q¼statistikpperptimme&_t_tags¼language:sv,siteid:40c776fe-7e5c-4838-841c-63d91e5a03c9,an-dquerymatch&_t_hit.id¼SVK_WebUI_Models_Pages_ArticlePage/_3936ae12-4e45-4dd5-a1a0-7ba2b30506e0_sv&_t_hit.pos¼3.10.09.2020.
- [128] Widén, J., and E. Wäckelgård. 2010. “A high-resolution stochastic model of domestic activity patterns and electricity demand.” *Applied Energy* 87 (2010):1880-1892.
- [129] NordPool, 2020. Historical Market Data [WWW Document], n.d. URL, <https://www.nordpoolgroup.com/historical-market-data/>. (accessed 28.10.2021)
- [130] Swedish Energy Markets Inspectorate, 2019. n.d. RER00607 Appendix 7 Discount rate for energy market, 2020–2023. [WWW Document] Available at URL <https://ei.se/bransch/reglering-av-natverksamhet/reglering---elnatsverksamhet/elnatsforetagens-intaktsramar-2020-2023/beslut-och-bilagor-elnatsforetagens-intaktsramar-2020-2023> (accessed 11.16.21).
- [131] Arvay, P., Muller, M.R., Ramdeen, V., et al.: ‘Economic implementation of the organic Rankine cycle in industry’. Conf. Proc. ACEEE Summer Study on Energy Efficiency in Industry 2011, Niagara Falls, NY, USA, 26–29 July 2011
- [132] Pieper, H., Ommen, T., Buhler, F., et al.: ‘Allocation of investment costs for large-scale heat pumps supplying district heating’, *Energy Procedia*, 2018, 147, pp. 358–367, doi:10.1016/j.egypro.2018.07.104

- [133] IVT Heat pumps, (2019). Technical facts and retail price for IVT Nordic Inverter SilverLine luft/vattenvärmepump [WWW Document], n.d. Available at <https://www.ivt.se/produkter/luftluftvarme/ivt-nordic-inverter-silver-line/fakta--priser/> (accessed 7 August 2019)
- [134] Viswanathan, V., Crawford, A., Stephenson, D., et al.: ‘Cost and performance model for redox flow batteries’, *J. Power Sources*, 2014, 247, pp. 1040–1051, doi:10.1016/j.jpowsour.2012.12.023
- [135] NordPool AS, 2021. System Price Curve Data [WWW Document], 2021. URL <https://www.nordpoolgroup.com/elspot-price-curves/> (accessed 9.10.21).
- [136] Hackl, R., administrator at the emissions trading unit at the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, 2021. E-mail correspondence.
- [137] Green Certificate Trading, 2021. Elcertifikat [WWW Document], n.d. . Ekonomifakta. URL <https://www.ekonomifakta.se/Fakta/Energi/Styrmedel/Elcertifikat/> (accessed 4.20.21).
- [138] The Swedish Tax Agency, 2021. Taxation of fuels (Skatt på bränsle) – In Swedish. [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.skatteverket.se/foretagochorganisationer/skatter/punktskatter/energiskatter/skattpabransle.4.15532c7b1442f256bae5e56.html> (accessed 4.20.21).
- [139] Swedish Government, 2021. Taxes on waste incineration. – In Swedish. Skatt på avfallsförbränning - Regeringen.se [WWW Document], n.d. URL <https://www.regeringen.se/rattsliga-dokument/lagratsremiss/2019/09/skatt-pa-avfallsforbranning/> (accessed 4.20.21).
- [140] Swedish Tax Agency, skatteverket.se, S., n.d. Skatt på el [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.skatteverket.se/foretag/skatterochavdrag/punktskatter/energiskatter/skattpael.4.15532c7b1442f256bae5e4c.html> (accessed 11.16.21).
- [141] Swedish Energy Market Inspectorate, 2018. Tekniska uppgifter - fjärrvärme [WWW Document], n.d. URL <https://ei.se/om-oss/statistik-och-oppnadata/tekniska-uppgifter--fjarrvarme> (accessed 11.26.21)
- [142] Sarbu, I., Sebarchievici, C., 2018. A Comprehensive Review of Thermal Energy Storage. *Sustainability* 10, 191. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su10010191>
- [143] Böttger, D., Götz, M., Lehr, N., Kondziella, H., Bruckner, T., 2014. Potential of the Power-to-Heat technology in district heating grids in Germany. *Energy Procedia* 46, 246–253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2014.01.179>
- [144] Schweiger, G., Rantzer, J., Ericsson, K., Lauenburg, P., 2017. The potential of power-to-heat in Swedish district heating systems. *Energy* 137, 661–669. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.02.075>
- [145] Mollenhauer E., Christidis A., Tsatsaronis G., 2017. Increasing the flexibility of combined heat and power plants with heat pumps and thermal energy storage. *Journal of Energy Resources Technology* 2017(140). American Society of Mechanical Engineers.
- [146] Bloess, A., Schill, W.-P., Zerrahn, A., 2018. Power-to-heat for renewable energy integration: A review of technologies, modeling approaches, and flexibility potentials. *Applied Energy* 212, 1611–1626. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.12.073>
- [147] Yu, Y., Chen, H., Chen, L., Chen, C., Wu, J., 2019. Optimal operation of the combined heat and power system equipped with power-to-heat devices for the improvement of wind energy utilization. *Energy Sci Eng* 7, 1605–1620. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ese3.375>
- [148] Hast, A., Rinne, S., Syri, S., Kiviluoma, J., 2017. The role of heat storages in facilitating the adaptation of district heating systems to large amount of variable renewable electricity *Energy* 137, 775-788. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.05.113>

- [149] Nuytten, T., Claessens, B., Paredis, K., Van Bael, J., Six, D., 2013. Flexibility of a combined heat and power system with thermal energy storage for district heating. *Applied Energy* 104, 583–591. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2012.11.029>
- [150] Dahl, M., Brun, A., Andresen, G.B., 2019. Cost sensitivity of optimal sector-coupled district heating production systems. *Energy* 166, 624–636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.10.044>
- [151] Lamaison, N., Collette, S., Vallée, M., Bavière, R., 2019. Storage influence in a combined biomass and power-to-heat district heating production plant. *Energy* 186, 115714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2019.07.044>
- [152] Åberg, M., Lingfors, D., Olauson, J., Widén, J., 2019. Can electricity market prices control power-to-heat production for peak shaving of renewable power generation? The case of Sweden. *Energy* 176, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2019.03.156>
- [153] #uppsalaeffekten [WWW Document], n.d. . Uppsala kommun. URL <https://www.uppsala.se/kommun-och-politik/sa-arbetar-vi-med-olika-amnen/sa-arbetar-vi-med-miljo-och-klimat/uppsalaeffekten/> (accessed 10.29.21).
- [154] CoordiNet [WWW Document], n.d. URL <https://energiforsk.se/program/coordinet/> (accessed 10.29.21).
- [155] Palensky, P., Dietrich, D., 2011. Demand Side Management: Demand Response, Intelligent Energy Systems, and Smart Loads. *IEEE Trans. Ind. Inf.* 7, 381–388. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2011.2158841>
- [156] Strbac, G., 2008. Demand side management: Benefits and challenges. *Energy Policy* 36, 4419–4426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2008.09.030>
- [157] Paulus, M., Borggreffe, F., 2011. The potential of demand-side management in energy-intensive industries for electricity markets in Germany. *Applied Energy* 88, 432–441. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2010.03.017>
- [158] Kies, A., Schyska, B., von Bremen, L., 2016. The Demand Side Management Potential to Balance a Highly Renewable European Power System. *Energies* 9, 955. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en9110955>
- [159] The FENIX vision: The virtual power plant and system integration of distributed energy resources, Contract no: SES6 – 518272, deliverable 1.4.0. Available: <http://www.fenix-project.org>. [Accessed 3 September 2020] [online]
- [160] Sowa, T., Kregel, S., Koopmann, S., Nowak, J., 2014. Multi-criteria Operation Strategies of Power-to-Heat-Systems in Virtual Power Plants with a High Penetration of Renewable Energies. *Energy Procedia* 46, 237–245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2014.01.178>
- [161] Lepiksaar, K., Mašatin, V., Latšov, E., Siirde, A., Volkova, A., 2021. Improving CHP flexibility by integrating thermal energy storage and power-to-heat technologies into the energy system. *Smart Energy* 2, 100022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segy.2021.100022>
- [162] Deecke, A., 2015. Usage of existing power plants as synchronous condenser. *ELECTROTECHNICAL REVIEW* 1, 66–68. <https://doi.org/10.15199/48.2015.10.12>
- [163] Oleksijs, R., Linkevics, O., 2019. Possible solutions for ancillary service provision from combined heat and power plants in Latvia, in: 2019 IEEE 60th International Scientific Conference on Power and Electrical Engineering of Riga Technical University (RTUCON). Presented at the 2019 IEEE 60th International Scientific Conference on Power and Electrical Engineering of Riga Technical University (RTUCON), IEEE, Riga, Latvia, pp. 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/RTUCON48111.2019.8982358>

- [164] Muratori, M., Calvin, K., Wise, M., Kyle, P., Edmonds, J., 2016. Global economic consequences of deploying bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS). *Environ. Res. Lett.* 11, 095004. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/11/9/095004>
- [165] Bioenergy International (2019). Stockholm Exergi to test carbon capture at Värtan bioenergy plant, 2019. Bioenergy International. URL <https://bioenergyinternational.com/heat-power/stockholm-exergi-to-test-carbon-capture-at-vartan-biomass-chp-plant> (accessed 8.9.19).
- [166] Champier, D., 2017. Thermoelectric generators: A review of applications. *Energy Conversion and Management* 140, 167–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.02.070>
- [167] Fujii, S., Kanematsu, Y., Kikuchi, Y., Nakagaki, T., Chiu, J.N.W., Martin, V., 2018. Techno economic analysis of thermochemical energy storage and transport system utilizing “Zeolite Boiler”: case study in Sweden. *Energy Procedia* 149, 102–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2018.08.174>
- [168] Krönauer, A., Lävemann, E., Brückner, S., Hauer, A., 2015. Mobile Sorption Heat Storage in Industrial Waste Heat Recovery. *Energy Procedia* 73, 272–280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2015.07.688>

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